

D5.1

Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results – Updated version V2.0 (M15)

White Research SRL (WR)

July 2025

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Abbreviations

RWAs	Remote Working Arrangements
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
WR	White Research
SMAAs	Social Media Accounts
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EU	European Union
AC	Associated Countries
UK	United Kingdom
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation

Executive Summary

This report presents the updated version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) for the Horizon Europe R-Map project in M15. The DCP continues to serve as a guiding framework for the consortium's dissemination and communication activities, updated to reflect the experience and outcomes achieved during the 15 months of implementation and optimised to drive greater impact through strategic, audience-focused outreach. Our goal remains to maintain a robust and coherent communication strategy, engaging all consortium members to maximise the project's impact.

Key enhancements include a more targeted, newsworthiness-driven communication approach (with students added as a core audience), a dedicated **Media Coverage** section and planned website upgrades. Robust monitoring and our new rapid-response breaking-news communication workflow ensure transparency, accountability and continuous improvement.

Furthermore, the report includes:

- A detailed overview of the dissemination and communication approach to date, showing how activities have been managed, monitored and adapted; the active involvement of the entire consortium has driven coordinated, effective outreach, with performance metrics in Section 8 (data as of 8 April 2025) illustrating our collaborative success.
- A sustained, organic, news-driven focus on engaging policymakers, industry leaders, remote workers, researchers, students and the general public, making R-Map's insights, results and key messages accessible and relevant across diverse target groups.

Transparency and accountability have remained fundamental. Robust monitoring mechanisms have been implemented to track dissemination actions, evaluate effectiveness and inform strategic adjustments when needed.

Looking ahead, the DCP will continue to guide dissemination efforts, building on lessons learned and ensuring that project results are communicated clearly, consistently and with impact. In summary, this document:

- ✓ **Reflects progress** made and lessons learned during the first 15 months.
- ✓ **Updates strategy, objectives** and activities based on real implementation experience.
- ✓ **Reaffirms** the roles and responsibilities of partners in dissemination.
- ✓ **Highlights** tools and communication channels used so far.
- ✓ **Revises** the internal monitoring, evaluation and reporting framework.
- ✓ **Updates the indicative timeline** of planned promotional actions.
- ✓ **Provides templates and guidelines** to ensure consistent and effective communication beyond the project's duration.

Dissemination and communication activities will continue throughout the project's lifecycle, with ongoing engagement across digital and physical platforms to support policy relevance, knowledge sharing, and stakeholder collaboration.

Disclaimer:

The methodology for the updated dissemination and communication plan of the R-Map project (Grant Agreement number: 101132497) draws upon established expertise, tools, and templates developed internally by White Research SRL, while also considering European Commission guidelines and best practices found in relevant literature. Elements of this methodology have been refined through previous research projects where White Research was involved, such as SKILLBILL (GA: 101075587) and SCENE (G.A: 101095303). This approach ensures efficient resource utilisation and alignment with project specifications. Customised adjustments were made to accommodate R-Map's unique requirements, EU recommendations and Grant Agreement conditions. This report outlines the adapted methodology as it was further developed and implemented within R-Map.

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope and Purpose

This deliverable presents the **updated Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)** for the Horizon Europe **R-Map** project. It provides a revised operational framework for the project's dissemination activities and reflects the experience and lessons learned during the first 15 months of implementation. The main purpose of this document is to guide the efficient and targeted communication and dissemination of R-Map's results, ensuring they are shared broadly, understood clearly and positioned for **long-term uptake and impact**.

The overarching objective of the DCP remains the same: to **increase the project's visibility**, enhance awareness among stakeholders and ensure that its outcomes are effectively communicated to target groups at local, regional, national and European levels. The DCP supports the consortium in aligning its messaging with the **contractual obligations of the European Commission**, while also enabling meaningful engagement with stakeholders in the public and private sectors, academic and civil society.

In particular, the updated version:

- Revisits the **strategic objectives** for communication and dissemination
- Defines key stakeholder groups and **tailored messaging approaches**
- Outlines the tools, channels and guidelines used so far
- Describes internal coordination and monitoring processes
- Highlights early outcomes and **adapts strategies** based on performance and feedback

Dissemination activities to date have focused on:

- Creating awareness about the project, its vision and goals
- Disseminating outcomes and knowledge at multiple levels
- Demonstrating the relevance and usefulness of R-Map results for policy and practice

Figure 1. Key directions of R-Map dissemination activities.

Our dissemination activities are carried out along three main directions: (i) creating awareness about the project, its vision, and activities; (ii) disseminating the project outcomes at local, national and international levels; and (iii) demonstrating the benefits and maximising impact of R-Map in order to foster the adoption of our outcomes among interested stakeholders.

Table 1. Key points addressed in the DCP

What?	Key messages
To Whom?	Target audiences
Who?	Roles & Responsibilities
How?	Communication tools and channels, guidelines, templates
When?	Timeline

Dissemination and communication activities are conducted under the dedicated Work Package 5 (WP5) and are overseen by White Research (WR), the project’s Dissemination and Communication Manager. All partners are expected to contribute actively by implementing their respective tasks, promoting R-Map through their networks and reporting actions regularly.

The DCP, along with its Annexes, templates and reporting mechanisms, remains a living document and will continue to evolve to reflect new insights and project developments. This updated version, delivered on Month 15 (M15), reflects the progress made during the first half of the project and thoughtfully incorporates updates to strengthen our dissemination and communication strategy. A final version will follow on Month 36 (M36) to ensure the continuity and sustainability of dissemination efforts beyond the project’s conclusion.

1.2 Updates to the DCP

R-Map’s updated Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) is intended to be a dynamic document, evolving to reflect the project’s progress during the first 15 months (M15). During the first half of the project, a series of activities have been implemented to raise awareness of R-Map and communicate its core messages to key stakeholder groups across Europe. Building on these activities and refinements introduced during the first 15 months, this updated version incorporates targeted updates driven by the review panel’s recommendations, ensuring our strategy remains impactful, audience-focused and aligned with newsworthiness criteria.

In this version, we have introduced the following key updates:

- **Dissemination & communication strategy.** Refined to follow an organic, newsworthiness-driven approach and to deploy targeted, strategic communications aligned with key research milestones.
- **Networks & synergies (new Section 5.3).** Partners have submitted local media and journalist contacts—enabling tailored, region-specific dissemination and communication outreach through their institutional and community networks.
- **Target audiences (Section 4.1).** Expanded to include **students** as a dedicated audience segment, with bespoke messages and channels.

- **Key messages (Section 4.2).** Messages have been refined and tailored to each stakeholder group ensuring clarity, relevance and strategic alignment, and explicitly linked to newsworthy project outputs and milestones.
- **Media Coverage (new Section 5.3).** A dedicated section cataloguing both general media outlets (e-newspapers, news agencies, newsletters, etc.) and niche or specialist publishers (focused on specific sectors such as labour markets, digitalisation, etc.).
- **Website enhancements (new Section 5.2.1.1).** Planned rollout of improved SEO, a researcher-profile directory, clear UK funding statement, an in-page sidebar explaining the “remote working” concept, downloadable presentation resources, and a dynamic **Media Corner** curating mainstream and niche coverage.
- We have implemented a **structured breaking-news process**, triggering on key milestones and outputs, drafting and reviewing summaries, and disseminating via our website, mailing list, social media and partner networks. This workflow ensures rapid, accurate announcements and feeds performance data back into our KPI dashboard for continuous improvement.
- **Monitoring & evaluation.** KPI dashboard refreshed with M15 data, updated stakeholder analytics and rapid-response workflow recommendations for future news-driven announcements.

Ongoing monitoring of performance indicators has allowed for an informed reassessment of the initial strategy. This version reflects refinements based on real-world engagement, ensuring that the DCP remains relevant, targeted and aligned with the evolving needs of the project.

While the initial strategy (M1-M15) had been proven solid, some targeted updates were introduced on M15 to better reflect R-Map’s progress and strengthen its outreach. These updates include:

- Dissemination and communication strategy (revised to reflect completed and upcoming activities)
- Promotional video (developed and launched in M6)
- Newsletter (2 editions published and shared, structure confirmed)
- Social media accounts (newly introduced Bluesky channel; updated performance data)
- Website (enhanced content, structure and analytics included)
- Internal and external events and conferences (detailed reporting of participation and results)
- Networks and synergies (ongoing task coordination and input from partners)
- Monitoring and evaluation (updated figures, KPIs and stakeholder analytics)

These updates aim to enhance the impact of R-Map’s outreach and support a consistent, well-coordinated communication approach as the project progresses toward its next milestones.

2. About R-Map

The rise of **RWAs** presents both opportunities and challenges, particularly concerning the urban-rural divide in Europe. Existing research suggests that RWAs can have significant socio-economic, spatial and environmental impacts. However, there's a need for a more comprehensive understanding of these effects and their implications for policy development. The goal of the R-Map project is to **investigate the influence of remote work on the urban-rural disparities across the entire EU-27 and AC** through comprehensive mapping, analysis, evaluation, and forecasting. R-Map collaborates closely with stakeholders to gain a thorough understanding of the impacts of remote work and offer data-driven solutions as well as contribute to the improvement of EU policies, rural development and sustainability. With a focus on social, spatial, and economic dimensions, R-Map addresses the persistent challenge of bridging the urban-rural gap, acknowledging its multifaceted nature and the impact of remote work on each dimension.

R-Map aims to analyse the impact of RWAs on the disparities between urban and rural regions in Europe.

Expected outcomes: The R-Map project aims to provide a holistic understanding of the social, economic, spatial and environmental implications of RWAs in urban and rural areas. By using a blend of state-of-the-art research techniques, scenario building, forecasting and modelling methodologies, **R-Map will enable policymakers to monitor and assess how RWAs affect people, communities, space, economy, and environment in urban and rural regions.** R-Map will also broaden our understanding of how RWAs affect living and working conditions, including health, safety and work-life balance aspects. Furthermore, the project seeks to analyse community responses and forecast scenarios to better understand societal adaptations to RWAs, aiming to bridge the urban-rural divide and promote resilient, inclusive communities. By providing evidence-based recommendations tailored to different regional contexts, the project will empower policymakers and businesses to shape remote working trends, address challenges and seize opportunities for sustainable economic development and inclusive growth.

By delving into the intricate dynamics of RWAs and their impact on urban and rural dynamics, **R-Map aims to enhance policy development and decision-making processes in the European Union (EU).** Through a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic, spatial and environmental effects of RWAs, the project aims to facilitate **the creation of more inclusive, resilient and sustainable communities.**

Consequently, the **main objectives** of the project are to:

- **Understand** current formats and manifestations of RWAs, as well as their potential socio-economic and spatial effects and their effects on working and living conditions.
- **Co-create an Integrated Impact Assessment Framework** to assess the individual and combined social, economic and spatial impacts of remote working (the 'R-Map' model).
- **Develop a visualisation platform** for decision makers that seek to understand how RWAs have affected people, communities, space, economy and environment in their region.

- **Forecast** the effects of RWAs, develop scenarios to combine them in plausible futures and evaluate their potential impacts in 6 regional use cases (2 cross-border).
- **Engage and empower policy makers** and other stakeholders in urban and rural areas to understand and influence the trends of remote work as well as to harness the opportunities arising.

Figure 2. R-Map's use cases

3. Dissemination and Communication Strategy

3.1 Overview

R-Map’s DCP described the overall D&C strategy of the project concerning the dissemination and communication of its outcomes. The strategy was carefully designed and tailored to the project’s approach, aiming to maximise its impact, transfer knowledge and results to targeted stakeholders and communicate the project’s concept to wider audiences. This strategy established clear guidelines for all dissemination activities throughout the project’s lifecycle, including key operational dissemination elements. These elements are illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 3. Overview of the R-Map dissemination and communication strategy.

This section presented the **overall D&C strategy** and outlined the **structure of the DCP**. The **first sub-section** defined the **objectives** used to monitor the successful implementation of the strategy. The **second sub-section** identified the **target audiences** for dissemination. The **next sub-section** presented the **key messages** for each group of stakeholders, as well as the **core visions and assets** of the project. A **dedicated sub-section** of the strategy focused on the **means, channels, and tools** used to reach the identified stakeholders. The **allocation of roles and responsibilities** and the **timelines** for the dissemination strategy were also clearly elaborated to ensure **smooth and effective implementation**.

Throughout the project, particular emphasis has been placed on establishing synergies with relevant initiatives at both national and European levels. Based on the work conducted under Task 5.3, this document provides an overview of the clustering and cooperation activities carried out to support this effort. Lastly, the **final**

chapter introduced a **solid framework** for assessing the **strategy's effectiveness**, along with a **timeline** for the implementation of dissemination and communication steps.

Aiming to ensure the successful dissemination and communication of results, the DCP constitutes a guidelines document that presents the tools and actions which will navigate the consortium partners to successfully engage the targeted stakeholders. **Of course, the DCP should not be seen as a static document but instead as a dynamic flexible strategy that will be reviewed and updated - if this is necessary - during the lifecycle of the project.**

3.2 Objectives of the DCP

The first version of R-Map's Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) outlined a comprehensive strategy that spans the entire duration of the project. It was designed to support the project's implementation by raising awareness of its activities and ensuring the visibility and uptake of its outcomes. The DCP functions as a horizontal tool connected to all work packages, with the aim of translating R-Map's vision into actionable communication steps targeting relevant stakeholder groups at multiple levels.

Overall, dissemination and communication activities contribute to promoting the project's actions and results, increasing the visibility of R-Map in key policy and research spaces, and enabling the uptake of its outcomes. The updated DCP continues to support the success of other work streams, the usability of project tools and results and the longer-term sustainability of the knowledge generated by the project. It clearly outlines expectations for each partner's contribution to communication tasks and helps guide efforts for greater outreach and impact.

In general, the D&C of R-Map aims to accomplish a number of high-level objectives:

- Present the **project's aim, vision, activities and events** to a wider audience
- Promote **awareness raising** among stakeholder groups
- Encourage **involvement** in the project's activities
- **Engage stakeholders** through a series of relevant activities, events and conferences
- Ensure that the **key messages are communicated** to its target audiences
- Ensure the **exploitation of the project's outcomes**.
- Introduce **scientific concepts in an easy to grasp way** to stakeholders and citizens
- **Plan, organise, run, monitor** and fine-tune the project's dissemination activities and events
- **Establish and sustain synergies** with other relevant national and European projects, initiatives and networks.
- Disseminate the project's **lessons learnt and outcomes** in an open and transparent way
- Establish an **active community exchanging ideas and knowledge** in topics relevant to the project.

To ensure the realization of the stated objectives, the dissemination and communication strategy focuses on executing a practical action plan with the aim of engaging a broad range of target audiences. It also emphasises

the provision of adaptable solutions when needed. A well-defined methodology outlining what is to be disseminated (vision, news, achievements, results), to whom (stakeholders, target groups), by what means (strategies, tools, channels), and when to disseminate constitutes a crucial element of an effective dissemination and communication (D&C) plan.

Considering these factors, the following steps for the dissemination and communication of the project are outlined:

- Establish the project's objectives and determine the communication channels and tools necessary for optimal visibility and promotion.
- Identify key messages and assets of the project.
- Associate each communication channel with the appropriate target group and define the tools and methods for project dissemination.
- Specify the roles and responsibilities of each partner to ensure active participation and effective management of the project's dissemination and communication activities.
- Monitor key dissemination indicators and make adjustments as needed.
- Define steps for the project's dissemination and communication activities and ensure their consistency with the overall timeline.

4. Target audiences and key messages

4.1 Target audience analysis

One of the primary objectives of the dissemination and communication activities of the R-Map project has been to effectively **reach and engage with key stakeholders** across various sectors, ensuring the widespread circulation of information about the project's vision, outcomes and solutions. This strategic approach aims to maximise the project's impact and the adoption of its results.

To this extent, **identifying and defining the target audience** has been crucial to tailor communication efforts effectively. The targeted stakeholders include a diverse range of professionals and entities with a significant interest in R-Map's objectives and activities. Specifically, R-Map has aimed to engage with Government and Policy Institutions, Business Associations and Decision Makers, Workers, Researchers & Academia (including Students), Urban Design and Development Experts and Civil Society.

Figure 4. R-Map's target audience

During the project's lifespan, it has remained important to classify the stakeholders in order to better prioritise and fine-tune our engagement efforts. Towards this aim, the **Stakeholders Classification Model** has been used to classify each targeted stakeholder group based on the following parameters:

- The extent of a stakeholder's power/authority
- The stakeholder's interest regarding the outcomes of the project
- The extent of the stakeholder's active involvement in the project
- The level of stakeholder's influence over the project planning and/or outcomes

The classification of the targeted stakeholders’ groups has helped the communicated messages and adopt the optimum tools and dissemination channels for each one of the groups. The following figure depicts the parameters and the way they define different types of stakeholder engagement.

Figure 5. Stakeholders Classification Model

R-Map has used the Stakeholders Classification Model to categorise its stakeholders to effectively, enabling the project to effectively prioritise and tailor its engagement strategies.

The D&C strategy has aimed to reach the above-mentioned identified audiences, which have been further categorised into the broader R-Map stakeholder groups. A more detailed elaboration on the targeted stakeholders and specific examples, is provided in the following Table:

Table 2. R-Map stakeholder examples

Target Group	Short Description	Sub - Categories	Examples
Government and Policy Institutions	Policy makers and government entities involved in shaping and implementing policies related to regional development, infrastructure, education, public health and cross-border taxation, among others.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International, national, regional, and local policy makers in EU & AC Policy advisors in regional and local development, infrastructure, education, public health, and cross-border taxation Agencies, projects Government and Policy Institutions, JRC, CEDEFOP, ELA, EIGE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Commission (EC) - Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy (DG REGIO): National Ministry of Regional Development European Parliament - Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EMPL) Academic and Research Institutions - Spatial Economics Research Centre (SERC), London School of Economics

Target Group	Short Description	Sub - Categories	Examples
Business Associations and Decision Makers	They play a crucial role in shaping economic policies and implementing innovative practices in sustainable resource management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry associations • Employers' unions • Chambers of commerce • SMEs • Business decision-makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Europe • European Association of Chambers of Commerce and Industry (EUROCHAMBERS) • European Round Table for Industry (ERT) • European Banking Federation (EBF)
Workers	Individuals that represent the workforce affected by regional transformations and play a vital role in shaping discussions on RWAs and their impacts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote and non-remote workers, • Labour unions • Digital nomads • Remote worker communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC) • Digital Nomads Hub • Global Workers Network • Remote Work Association (RWA) • National Association of Virtual Workers (NAVW)
Researchers & Academia (including Students)	A group which offers valuable insights and knowledge to R-Map's research endeavours, facilitating a deeper understanding of regional transformations and their implications. This group also includes students, who represent the next generation of researchers and contribute fresh perspectives, innovation, and academic engagement to the project's knowledge ecosystem.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professors • Researchers, experts in spatial, socioeconomic, environmental analysis, infrastructure and technology • Students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Research Council (ERC): • European Association of Geographers (EUROGEO): • European Urban Research Association (EURA) • European Spatial Planning Observation Network (ESPON) • Association of European Schools of Planning for Researchers and Academia (AESOP) • AESOP Young Academics Network • European Students' Union (ESU)
Urban Design and Development Experts	This group plays a vital role in shaping urban landscapes and infrastructure, offering expertise on how to adapt spaces to accommodate the consequences of regional transformations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban planners • Real Estate Agents • Architects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Urban Knowledge Network (EUKN) • European Council of Spatial Planners (ECTP-CEU) • European Network of Architects' Competent Authorities (ENACA) • International Federation for Housing and Planning (IFHP)

Target Group	Short Description	Sub - Categories	Examples
Civil Society	A group that contributes to social change and community development, aiming to address societal challenges and promote sustainable practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens • Advocacy officers • NGOs • CSOs • Local communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Federation of National Organisations Working with the Homeless (FEANTSA) • European Public Health Alliance (EPHA) • European Federation of Ethical and Alternative Banks (FEBEA) • European Women’s Lobby (EWL)

4.2 R-Map Key-messages

In formulating an effective Dissemination and Communication strategy for R-Map, a fundamental aspect has been the ability to convey key messages in a way that resonates with diverse stakeholder groups. As emphasised in the previous section, identifying and understanding these stakeholders has been essential for crafting messages that address their unique needs and interests.

Given the dynamic nature of the project, ongoing refinement of these messages is essential, informed by ongoing activities and feedback loops. Moreover, R-Map has benefited from the collective expertise and networks of its consortium partners, enabling robust engagement across various sectors.

While the table below provides an initial framework for tailored messages, the evolution of key messages throughout R-Map's lifecycle continues to be guided by real-world insights and project outcomes.

Table 3. R-Map’s target audience needs and messages

Target	Needs	Messages
Government and Policy Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To understand the effects of RWAs. •To develop tailored Policy Strategies. •To gain access to updated data and tools. •To address the Urban-Rural Divides. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Discover R-Map’s (WP4) findings on how Remote Work Arrangements reshape regional development and strengthen territorial cohesion •Incorporate R-Map’s evidence-based recommendations (Task 4.3) and our policy roundtable to strengthen strategic planning at regional and national levels. •Tap into our open-access visualisation platform (launching 2026) for up-to-date territorial datasets and interactive tools, monitor and assess RWAs’ effects on communities, economies and environments in real time. •Collaborate to address urban–rural divides using R-Map’s spatial analysis and best practice examples, which will be shared in upcoming policy briefs.
Business Associations and Decision Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To understand the implications of RWAs. •To advocate for clear government regulations. •To foster collaboration and knowledge exchange. •To access tailored support mechanisms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Unlock economic gains by embracing remote work, with R-Map’s sector-specific insights showing how it can affect productivity, talent retention, and regional competitiveness. •Shape the future of work by joining R-Map’s cross-regional stakeholder events. These contributions will inform our policy recommendations and help build effective frameworks. •Implement responsible remote work using our upcoming R-Map platform, gain step-by-step guidance to adopt and manage remote work strategies that drive business performance and uphold best practices.

Target	Needs	Messages
<p>Workers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To understand the implications of RWAs. •To access support for transitioning to remote work. •To advocate for fair and equitable treatment. •To foster a sense of community and belonging. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discover how RWAs impact your work and life by joining R-Map’s cross-regional dialogues. Gain insights into the social and economic effects of remote work on your career and wellbeing. • Access our digital toolkit to explore the opportunities and challenges of remote work, equipping you with practical tips and resources to thrive in a remote environment. • Join the conversation at R-Map’s stakeholder events and on social media, help shape fair remote-work policies, connect with peers and foster a supportive community.
<p>Researchers & Academia (including Students)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To access updated methodologies and data to effectively analyse phenomena related to RWAs. •To advance research in scientific fields related to the project. •To understand the effects of RWAs on various socio-economic and environmental factors. •To gain exposure to real-world research projects and develop skills relevant to regional transformation and interdisciplinary analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access cutting-edge data and methods via R-Map’s interdisciplinary visualisation platform analysing RWAs across socio-economic and environmental dimensions. • Engage in knowledge exchange and collaboration via R-Map’s upcoming workshops, cross-regional dialogues, and policy roundtable that bring together researchers, academia, and policymakers to bridge science and practice. • Participate actively in R-Map’s research activities (WP3 and WP4), contributing to cutting-edge insights on RWAs. • Leverage evidence-based findings from R-Map’s forthcoming publications and policy briefs to support research and help shape regional transformation strategies. • Read our project update in the ICOH Newsletter, an overview of R-Map’s latest findings and scope, delivering actionable insights on remote work’s occupational health and safety impacts directly to your inbox. • Provide opportunities for students to participate in research, build professional networks, and contribute fresh perspectives to the study of RWAs.

Target	Needs	Messages
<p>Urban Design and Development Experts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To access innovative urban planning strategies and tools that accommodate the consequences of regional transformations. •To collaborate with stakeholders and experts across various disciplines. •To gain insights into best practices and case studies related to urban design and development in the context of RWAs. •To contribute expertise and innovative solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate remote work into urban planning using R-Map’s insights on workspace, infrastructure and land-use. • Shape sustainable and inclusive urban landscapes, informed by data-driven findings from R-Map’s spatial and socio-economic analysis. • Learn from successful case studies showcasing innovative approaches and successful integration of remote working considerations into urban planning strategies, featuring examples of how cities and regions are adapting to the challenges and opportunities brought by RWAs. • Engage in cross-disciplinary collaboration through R-Map’s stakeholder dialogues and workshops, providing a platform for urban professionals to share expertise and contribute solutions to spatial challenges posed by shifting work patterns.
<p>Civil Society</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Emphasize the importance of integrating remote working considerations into urban planning and development processes. •Highlight the role of urban design and development experts in shaping sustainable and inclusive urban landscapes. •Showcase innovative approaches and case studies that demonstrate successful integration of remote working considerations into urban planning strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stay informed on RWAs’ social and economic impacts; follow R-Map’s upcoming reports and social media updates to understand the opportunities and risks remote work brings to your community. • Shape inclusive remote-work policies by participating in R-Map’s regional dialogues and make sure your concerns and priorities are heard. • Collaborate with local authorities and policymakers to address rural development challenges and promote inclusive growth through remote working initiatives. • Discover community-led solutions in our articles and social posts and see how real-world examples from R-Map’s findings demonstrate remote work’s potential for social cohesion and regional resilience.

5. Dissemination and Communication Tools and Channels

Aligned with the core goals of the R-Map project, the DCP embraces a versatile approach, making use of a variety of tools and channels to raise awareness about the project’s activities and achievements. Through this strategic use of communication methods, R-Map aims to promote the adoption of responsible remote work practices. Below is an overview of the tools, channels and activities already in use or planned, illustrating how the D&C strategy continues to support the project’s objectives.

Figure 6. R-Map Dissemination and Communication Channels.

The R-Map promotional material and graphical identity includes:

- Project’s logo
- Project’s visual and graphical identity
- Trifold leaflet
- Poster
- Presentation template
- Promotional videos
- Ad hoc promotional material (tailored to the project’s activities and needs – if required)

The R-Map online presence includes:

- Web portal
- R-Map Platform
- Facebook page
- X account (former Twitter)

- BlueSky account
- LinkedIn profile
- YouTube channel

The R-Map events include:

- Cross- regional dialogues
- Policy Workshops
- Final dissemination event
- Engagements events
- External events & conferences
- Clustering & Synergy meeting

The R-Map publications include:

- Project’s deliverables
- Scientific Publications
- Newsletters
- Press releases
- Policy briefs & Recommendations
- Other publications in different media.

Specific tools and channels will be used for communicating and disseminating the project’s activities and outcomes to the identified target groups. They are presented below in a summarised way:

Table 4. Tools and channels used for the identified target groups

Target Groups	Tools and Channels
Government and Policy Institutions	Policy workshops, Cross- regional dialogues, Website, platform, Project tools, Synergies with EU initiatives
Business Associations and Decision Makers	Web portal, platform, promotional material, SMAs, audio-visuals, Cross-regional dialogues
Workers	Cross-regional dialogues, Website, platform, SMAs

Researchers & Academia	Website and platform, Cross-regional dialogues, Promotional Material, SMAs, conferences
Urban Design and Development Experts	Web portal, platform, Promotional material, SMAs, audio-visuals, Cross-regional dialogues
Civil Society	Website and platform, SMAs, audio-visuals, Cross-regional dialogues

5.1 Promotional material

The promotional material for R-Map was prepared during the early stages of the project. WR was responsible for the graphic design and the content, while the consortium partners offered feedback throughout the development process. The material is freely available to the public through the project’s website (online for download) and the partners will print it when needed. The material is used during physical activities (including external and project events) to attract and engage relevant stakeholders and give more information on the project’s mission and objectives.

The project logo, in conjunction with the general graphic elements and the aesthetic concept, is what distinguishes the project and serves as the foundation for the further development of the entire promotion package (e.g. leaflets, posters, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, web-portal, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.) that will be used in all dissemination and communications activities. During M1, the project partners were invited to participate in an online voting for the project’s logo, where a variety of logo options were presented to them. The below figure illustrates the final logo of the project:

Figure 7. R-Map logo

R-Map’s Logo clearly reflects the contrast between urban and rural settings.

The chosen colour palette for R-Map's promotional materials is a reflection of the project's core values and objectives. Each colour was meticulously chosen to convey distinct qualities that resonate with our mission.

Collectively, they symbolise our commitment to innovation, sustainability, reliability and inclusivity. This palette serves as a visual representation of our dedication to advancing research and innovation in our field while fostering collaboration and inclusiveness among stakeholders.

Figure 8. The colour palette of R-Map's logo

The R-Map logo should be visible to all the communication material produced in the framework of the project (presentation, deliverables etc.). Similarly, the EU funding should be properly acknowledged, and the EU emblem should also be properly depicted in all communication material.

Figure 9. The emblem of the European Union

All the promotional material is designed based on the project's unique identity.

5.1.1 Leaflet and Poster

The promotional material for R-Map was meticulously crafted during the project's initial stages, with WR overseeing graphic design and content creation, incorporating feedback from consortium partners. These materials encapsulate the essence of R-Map's mission and objectives. Available for download on the project website and printable upon request, they are deployed during physical events to engage stakeholders. Central to the promotional package is the project logo, chosen through a collaborative online voting process among partners during M1. The logo's colour palette, featuring carefully chosen hues, reflects R-Map's dedication to research and innovation, offering a visually compelling representation of our values and aspirations.

CURRENT SITUATION

Remember when the pandemic struck in 2020 and many of us suddenly found ourselves in the world's largest remote work experiment? Nowadays, while many companies adopt return to office policies, a significant number of employees continue to work remotely. This shift has significantly changed the way we work and live, affecting the divide between cities and rural areas. Our leaders and policymakers need to act fast; they need to embrace the positive aspects of remote work and find solutions for the challenges it brings to meet the changing demands of the future workforce.

THE CHALLENGE

Despite the widespread adoption of remote work, there's still much we don't know about its impact on our communities and the relationship between urban and rural areas. This lack of knowledge leaves policymakers and businesses without crucial insights needed to make informed decisions. How does remote work affect various demographic groups? What are the long-term social, spatial and economic effects? What are the most suitable strategies to address the growing urban-rural divide? These are some of the key questions R-MAP is going to tackle.

CONTACT DETAILS:

Programme: Horizon Europe
 Type of action: BIA
 Duration: 36 months (01/02/2024 - 31/01/2027)
 Budget (EU contribution): 2 988 223,75
 Grant Agreement: 101032497
 Project Coordinator: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
 Prof. Ekaterina Stylianidou: esty@auth.gr

OUR TEAM:

ARISTOTELIAN UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI, arx.net, EDC UNIVERSITÄT, METREX, Q-PLAN, R+M, REM%TE, UNIVERSITY OF SURREY, UNIVERSITÀ BOCCHIONI, UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE, WHITE

FOLLOW US: X, Facebook, LinkedIn, RMAP Project EU

CONTACT US: www.rmap-project.eu, info@rmap-project.eu

Funded by the European Union

R-Map
 ADDRESS THE EFFECTS OF REMOTE WORKING ARRANGEMENTS IN URBAN AND RURAL AREAS

Urban-rural unity, through digital opportunity

Figure 10. R-Map leaflet exterior part

R-MAP'S APPROACH

R-Map aims to explore how remote work affects the urban-rural gap in Europe by mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of remote working arrangements. R-Map uses state-of-the-art research methods and works closely with stakeholders to fully understand the impacts of remote work and provide data-driven solutions. By integrating various data sources and advanced modelling techniques, the project intends to prepare us for future trends. Focusing on social, spatial and economic aspects, the project tackles the ongoing challenge of bridging the urban-rural gap, recognizing its complexity and the influence of remote work on each aspect.

WHO WILL BENEFIT FROM THE PROJECT

- Policy makers seeking data-driven solutions for the urban-rural gap.
- Company decision makers navigating the transition to remote work.
- Communities affected by changes in work dynamics.
- Individuals seeking remote working arrangements and improved quality of life.
- The academic and scientific community gaining access to under-researched aspects and dimensions of remote work.

R-MAPS USE CASES

- Netherlands-Germany:** Examining cross-border commuting and regional development impacts.
- Austria-Switzerland:** Studying cross-border remote work implications for taxation, social security and mobility.
- Surrey, UK:** Exploring impacts on housing, transportation and community well-being.
- Milano, Italy:** Analysing spatial, economic and social changes derived from remote work.
- Thessaloniki, Greece:** Investigating the effects of remote work on housing, migration and urban dynamics.
- Istanbul, Turkey:** Assessing housing, commuting and business model changes, health and wellbeing services needs due to remote work.

R-MAP'S OBJECTIVES

- Gain insights into current remote working arrangements and impact on working and living conditions.
- Develop a framework to assess the social, economic and spatial impacts of remote work.
- Create a user-friendly platform for decision-makers to visualize remote work impact and trends.
- Predict the effects of remote work and evaluate their potential impacts in 6 regional use cases.
- Engage policymakers and stakeholders in shaping the future of work.
- Communicate & Deploy synergies.

Figure 11. R-Map leaflet interior part

IN A NUTSHELL

R-Map aims to explore how remote work affects the urban-rural gap in Europe by mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the social, spatial and economic effects of remote working arrangements. We use state-of-the-art research methods and work closely with stakeholders to fully understand the impacts of remote work and provide solutions. Our aim is to provide practical insights and strategies empowering policymakers and communities to better shape the trends of remote working in their territory. Join us in shaping the future of work across Europe!

Urban-rural unity,
through digital opportunity

CORE ELEMENTS OF THE PROJECT

- 6 Regional Use Cases
- Large-scale survey and impact assessments
- R-Map Model for impact assessment
- Regional typology & taxonomy of RWAs
- Forecasting Scenarios
- Policy workshops & recommendations

R-MAPS USE CASES

R-MAP'S OBJECTIVES

- » Understand current remote work practices.
- » Assess social, economic, and spatial impacts.
- » Visualize remote work trends for decision-makers.
- » Forecast future effects of remote work.
- » Engage stakeholders in policy dialogue.
- » Communicate research findings effectively.

OUR TEAM

Visit: www.r-map.eu | Contact us: info@r-map.eu | Follow us: [R-MAP Project EU](#)

Figure 12. R-Map Poster

5.1.2 Publication Templates

In managing project documents and communication, the R-Map initiative has put together a set of templates to keep a consistent and easily recognisable look during dissemination activities. The developed templates include:

- **R-Map Presentation Template:** Designed for consortium partners, this template finds utility in various events and meetings, ensuring a unified visual representation.
- **Reports Template:** Tailored for project deliverables and publications, this template adheres to the project's graphical identity, fostering consistency in documentation.
- **Letterheads** (to be used for official invitation to events)

The strategic integration of these templates not only upholds visual uniformity but also contributes to the overall recognisability of the R-Map project. As a crucial part of the DCP, these templates go through continuous refinement.

Figure 13. R-Map's Report Template and Letterheads

Figure 14. R-Map's Presentation Template

5.1.3 Promotional Videos

As part of R-Map’s Dissemination and Communication Plan, two professional promotional videos have been foreseen to support the project’s visibility, engagement and impact. These videos aim to introduce R-Map’s objectives, highlight key findings and foster interest among stakeholders and the wider public.

The **first promotional video** was developed and released in **Month 6 (July 2024)**. It presents a clear and engaging overview of R-Map’s vision, objectives and thematic focus, offering a compelling introduction to the project for a wide audience. Designed to be concise and accessible, the video communicates the project’s core messages through dynamic visuals and a well-structured narrative.

The video production process followed a collaborative and structured approach. WR drafted the **initial script**, outlining the narrative and key phrases to highlight R-Map’s goals and relevance. This draft was shared with partners for feedback, which was integrated into the revised version. A **storyboard** was then developed with input from the video production team and reviewed by the consortium before finalisation. The animated video was subsequently produced and published.

The video was disseminated through the **R-Map website, YouTube channel** and the project’s **social media platforms** where it serves as an engaging visual introduction to the project and its thematic focus on remote working arrangements and regional transformation. The consortium also actively contributed to its visibility by sharing the video through their own networks and organisational channels.

A **second promotional video** is planned for release in **Month 36 (M36)**, which will present R-Map’s key research findings, policy recommendations, and broader impact across its regional case studies.

These videos contribute to making R-Map’s work more accessible and are designed to resonate with both expert audiences and the general public.

Figure 15. Screenshots from R-Map's video

5.2 Digital Presence

Gradually, more people choose to get informed through digital communication channels. To better communicate its messages, R-Map will focus on building a strong online presence in multiple digital platforms aiming to reach as many and diverse stakeholders as possible. To this end, R-Map has developed:

- (i) a website
- (ii) a bi-annual newsletter
- (iii) SMAs

5.2.1 R-Map’s Website

The development of the [R-Map website](#), launched in **Month 3 (April 2024)**, has been a core element of the project’s communication and dissemination strategy. As the project’s primary digital hub, the website serves both as a platform for informing the public and stakeholders and as a repository for project outcomes and updates. It ensures **easy and direct access** to all essential information about R-Map, including its vision, objectives, methodology, activities and results.

Figure 16. R-Map’s website proposed structure

The website was designed with **user-friendliness and accessibility** in mind, aiming to reach a broad and diverse audience. It presents information in a clear and structured manner, making it easy for visitors to explore the project’s progress, partners, regional use cases, deliverables and events.

Since its launch, the website has been regularly updated with **project news, milestones, event announcements, public deliverables** and **communication materials** such as leaflets, posters and the

promotional video. A dedicated section has also been created to host the **bi-annual newsletter**, which is downloadable free of charge.

The R-Map website was developed using **WordPress** with the Avada theme and has been optimised for responsiveness and compatibility across devices, including mobile phones and tablets. Its architecture ensures consistent user experience while maintaining compliance with accessibility standards. Throughout the project's lifecycle, the website continues to function as a **living platform**, reflecting the evolving nature of R-Map and ensuring that both consortium members and external stakeholders can stay informed and engaged.

Website Homepage

Figure 17. R-Map's website homepage

R-Map's approach, methodology, key stakeholders and consortium website sections

Figure 18. R-Map's Methodology - website screenshot

Our Approach:

R-Map aims to explore how remote work affects the urban-rural gap in Europe by mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of remote working arrangements. R-MAP uses state-of-the-art research methods and works closely with stakeholders to fully understand the impacts of remote work and provide data-driven solutions. By integrating various data sources and advanced

modelling techniques, the project intends to prepare us for future trends. Focusing on social, spatial and economic aspects, the project tackles the ongoing challenge of bridging the urban-rural gap, recognizing its complexity and the influence of remote work on each aspect.

R-Map employs an innovative Integrated Impact Assessment Framework, drawing on spatial, statistical and machine learning techniques to comprehensively analyse the effects of remote working arrangements on the urban-rural divide at the regional level.

Integrative Methodology

Building on existing research, R-Map advances the field by integrating diverse data sources, including large-scale surveys, open datasets and crowdsourced data. By employing a transdisciplinary approach, we aim to capture the multifaceted impacts of remote work on social, economic and spatial dimensions.

Advanced Modelling

Our framework utilizes sophisticated statistical and machine learning algorithms to analyse complex relationships and correlations within the data. By training and validating the model across diverse regional contexts within the EU, we ensure its robustness and applicability across different scenarios.

Figure 19. R-Map's approach – website screenshot

Figure 20. R-Map's Key Stakeholders - website screenshot

Figure 21. R-Map's mission - website screenshot

Figure 22. R-Map's consortium section - website screenshot

Deliverables website section

Figure 23. Deliverables section – website screenshot

Project’s News website section

Figure 24. Project’s news- website screenshot

R-Map's Synergies website section

Synergies

MOBI-TWIN

UNIVERSITY OF SURREY

remaking
Remote-Working Multiple Impacts
in the Age of Disruptions:
Socioeconomic Transformations,
Territorial Rethinking, and Policy Actions

**WinWin4
WorkLife**

MOBI-TWIN is an EU-funded project dedicated to unravelling the dynamics of spatial mobility and its significant impact on European Union regions. The project aims to understand the intricate patterns of mobility and leverage this knowledge to foster regional prosperity.

The Future of Work Research Centre leads innovative interdisciplinary research on evolving work relationships and the factors driving these changes. Its work focuses on understanding the impact of these shifts on organizational effectiveness and human well-being, emphasizing the role of work in fostering inclusive, prosperous, and fair societies

REMAKING aims to deliver a policy-oriented framework reflecting the new and multi-faceted realities of remote working, facilitating policymakers to adopt place-based policies balancing the opportunities and risks of remote working and sharing practices to foster mutual learning on remote working in the novel scenario of megatrends and shocks.

WinWin4WorkLife seeks to foster sustainable remote working arrangements (RWA) in Europe by integrating employer and employee perspectives to promote a healthy, inclusive and sustainable work-life balance across various urban, rural, and cross-border settings. The project will collect novel and comprehensive data in 5 European countries, selected to represent different welfare systems, housing and labour markets, and cultural norms towards remote work.

[Find out more](#)

[Find out more](#)

[Find out more](#)

[Find out more](#)

Figure 25. Synergies section – website screenshot

Press Corner section

Press Corner

Welcome to the R-Map Press Corner, your go-to hub for the latest news, updates, and insights on our efforts to assess the impacts of remote working across Europe. Here, you'll find a comprehensive collection of press releases, interviews, and media coverage showcasing our work on bridging the urban-rural divide, improving remote work practices, and driving sustainable policy changes. Stay informed about R-Map's progress and key milestones as we continue to shape the future of work.

[Read here!](#)

[Read here!](#)

Figure 26. Press Corner section - website screenshot

Advisory Board section

Figure 27. Advisory Board section – website screenshot (1)

Figure 28. Advisory Board section - website screenshot (2)

Use Cases section

Figure 29. Use Cases section - website screenshots

Overall, the R-Map website has steadily gained visibility among stakeholders and the wider public. As of April 2025, it has recorded 878 unique visitors and over 3,200 page views, reflecting early engagement with the project’s content and structure. Among the most visited sections are the homepage, *Advisory Board* and *Our Team*, suggesting that users are particularly interested in the consortium’s composition and the expertise driving the project forward.

The project’s digital dissemination efforts have been ongoing since the website’s launch, contributing to its visibility and reach. In particular, several targeted actions have supported the platform’s growth:

- **Regular content updates**, including internal and external news, project milestones, event announcements and insights related to remote working and territorial development.
- **Timely publication of materials**, such as public deliverables, the project factsheet, brochures and the promotional video.
- **Cross-promotion via social media**, where new website content is actively disseminated through R-Map’s LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter) and Facebook pages.
- **Linkage to social media**, with published articles and announcements on the website systematically shared across the project’s social channels to maximise visibility and drive traffic back to the site.
- **Dedicated stakeholder sections**, including the *Advisory Board* page, which highlights external expertise and enhances the project's credibility and transparency.

- **User-oriented design**, featuring a WordPress-based structure optimised for accessibility, mobile compatibility, and intuitive navigation.

While reaching the KPI of 10,000 visits remains a longer-term goal, the steady performance so far demonstrates growing awareness of R-Map's work. Website analytics are actively monitored to inform content strategy and ensure the platform continues to serve as an effective tool for stakeholder engagement.

5.2.1.1 Planned Website Enhancements (M20-M21)

To improve the overall effectiveness of the R-Map website as both a communication tool and an engagement platform, several updates and additions are proposed. These enhancements aim to increase the website's usability for visitors, improve its visibility in search engines, and strengthen its role in engaging key stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and the general public. By addressing **both technical and content-related aspects**, the goal is to ensure that the website better reflects the scope and ambition of the project while serving as a dynamic and accessible resource. Specifically, the following updates are planned to be carried out on M20-M21:

- **Review SEO (Search Engine Optimisation):**
A review and update of SEO settings will be carried out on M20-M21. The website's visibility in search engine results for terms like "rmap" and "r-map" will be enhanced, by adding targeted meta-tags and keywords (e.g. 'R-Map', 'remote work policy', etc.). These updates will improve discoverability across major search engines.
- **Researcher Profiles addition in the "Our Team" Section:**
Since the "Our Team" page receives significant traffic, a new sub-section titled "**Researcher Profiles**" will be added. Each profile may include a photo of the researcher, name, role/title, short bio, and a button hyperlinked to an external online profile (e.g., institutional page, LinkedIn, etc.) This would offer more visibility to the researchers and foster stronger engagement with visitors interested in the people behind the project.
- **Funding Sources clarification:**
The website will clearly communicate all relevant funding sources, including UK funding statement. To this end, we will add the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) logo alongside the European Union logo, accompanied by the following disclaimer:
"UK participants in the Horizon Europe project [R-Map] are supported by UKRI grant number [10106145] (University of Surrey)."
- **Explain Key Terms for General Audiences:**
The website will include an embedded definition of "remote working" in a sidebar or pop-up, with links to more detailed explanations or resources for non-expert audiences.
- **Media Corner category addition:**
A Media Corner will be added to highlight external media coverage related to R-Map. This section could focus on: external articles, interviews, or podcasts mentioning the project and media appearances by consortium members.
- **Presentations:**

Conferences presentations -as a resource- could be uploaded on R-Map's website, at partners' discretion. While hosting full slide decks offers valuable dissemination, we recognise that large file volumes may degrade site performance and page load times. As an alternative, we consider integrating key highlights or summaries from these presentations into narrative-style news articles, developed in collaboration with the partners involved. This approach enables us to share the core messages and outcomes of R-Map's contributions to external events in an accessible and engaging narrative format, while preserving the overall speed and stability of the site. Full presentation files can still be made available upon request to interested stakeholders ensuring transparency and access without compromising website speed or stability.

To validate the technical feasibility of these enhancements, WR engaged the external development team responsible for the development of R-Map's website. Their assessment confirms that all proposed updates align with the existing infrastructure and adhere to best practices in content management, user engagement and SEO. The updates are also not expected to interfere with the website's performance, stability, or day-to-day operations. Overall, the suggested updates present an opportunity to improve user experience and strengthen the website's function as a dynamic and accessible platform for communication with key audiences.

5.2.2 Newsletter

As part of R-Map's multi-channel communication strategy, a **bi-annual newsletter** has been established to ensure regular engagement with the project's community. The newsletter is intended to reach a broad audience, including stakeholders who may not be active on social media or closely following ongoing project activities. It offers a curated overview of project updates, future plans and relevant sectoral insights in a clear and accessible format.

The newsletter is developed and distributed using **Mailchimp**, managed by **White Research**, with content contributions coordinated across the consortium. Prior to each release, partners are invited to share updates from the tasks and activities they lead, and to provide feedback on the newsletter's content and structure.

While each issue is tailored to current project developments, the newsletter generally includes the following sections:

- **Introduction:** A brief recap of the project and highlights from two consortium members.
- **Progress Updates:** Key developments, project meetings and milestone achievements.
- **Current Activities:** A snapshot of tasks that are ongoing or recently completed.
- **Future Developments:** Upcoming events, deliverables and activities.
- **Synergies:** Updates on collaboration with related projects or initiatives.
- **Sector News:** Broader insights and trends related to remote work, digital transitions, and territorial development.

So far, two newsletters have been published and distributed via Mailchimp to all subscribers. Each issue has also been uploaded to the **dedicated newsletter section of the R-Map website**, where visitors can explore

previous editions or subscribe to receive future updates. In full alignment with **GDPR requirements**, the subscription process includes explicit consent and users may unsubscribe at any time. The newsletter serves as a valuable communication tool that complements R-Map’s digital presence, supporting sustained stakeholder engagement throughout the project’s lifecycle.

So far, 2 newsletters have been published and distributed via Mailchimp to all subscribers

Figure 30. R-Map's newsletter section in project's website

This Privacy Policy applies to R-MAP project website and governs personal data collection and use by the website only. R-MAP project is committed to being transparent and to ensuring your privacy is protected. By using our website, you consent to personal data practices described below. R-MAP project Privacy Policy is effective from 26/04/2024. We reserve the right to update or change the policy at any time, therefore you may want to review it periodically.

Figure 31. R-Map's Privacy Policy on project's website

Below are snapshots from the first two editions of the R-Map newsletter, showcasing the layout, visual identity and thematic structure used to communicate project updates to the wider community:

Figure 32. R-Map's 1st Newsletter – Screenshots

Figure 33. R-Map's 2nd newsletter - Screenshots

The R-Map Newsletter is sent to all subscribers upon its release and is also published on the project's website. It has proven to be an effective dissemination and communication tool for reaching digital audiences and maintaining visibility across project updates. As of M12, the R-Map newsletter has attracted 101 subscribers. With engagement activities set to intensify in the upcoming months a steady increase in the subscriber base is anticipated.

5.2.3 Social Media Accounts

Social media channels continue to be a key part of R-Map's dissemination and communication strategy. As widely used and flexible tools, they allow for real-time engagement, help promote project activities and support the growth of an online community around R-Map's mission. They also help bring more traffic to the R-Map website by sharing project updates, sector news and promotional content.

By Month 2 (March 2024), the project had launched official accounts on [Facebook](#), [X](#) (formerly Twitter), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#). Each of these platforms is used to reach different types of audiences and plays a role in increasing the visibility of R-Map's work online.

The accounts are managed by White Research, with input from partners to help share milestones, promote events and post about project progress. Posts are planned in line with the project's communication calendar and shared regularly to keep the audience engaged.

In March 2025, **the project added a new channel on Bluesky** to further strengthen its social media presence. This decision was made in response to the evolving digital communication landscape. In alignment with the European Commission's emphasis on transparency and open dialogue, Bluesky was identified as a valuable complementary channel. Its decentralised structure and focus on user control offer additional opportunities to engage stakeholders and diversify outreach efforts, supporting the project's broader communication goals.

As of M15, all channels are active and continue to support stakeholder engagement, help spread the project's key messages and build visibility that will last beyond the project's duration.

The target audiences addressed by each social media channel and the specific objectives are presented in the following table:

Table 5. The target audiences addressed by each social media channel.

SMA	Target Audience	Objectives
Facebook 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy makers, public administration, EU institutions • Business & industry: employers • Workers • Researchers and academia • Civil society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminate project updates, policy recommendations and research findings to policymakers and government entities. • Engage with businesses and industry stakeholders to promote sustainable practices and innovation. • Provide resources and information on regional transformations and their impacts to workers. • Share research insights and academic publications with the research community. • Raise awareness among civil society groups about regional development and sustainability issues.
X (former Twitter) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy makers, public administration, EU institutions • Business & industry: employers • Workers • Researchers and academia • Civil society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share concise updates, news and insights related to R-Map's objectives and outcomes. • Foster dialogue and networking opportunities among diverse stakeholders. • Amplify key messages and research findings to a broader audience. • Engage with policymakers and industry leaders to solicit feedback and support. • Promote community engagement and participation in regional sustainability initiatives.
LinkedIn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy makers, public administration, EU institutions • Business & industry: employers • Researchers and academia • Business and industry: urban planners, real estate agents, architects • Civil society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultivate professional relationships and discussions on sustainable regional development. • Share in-depth analysis, reports, and articles relevant to R-Map's objectives. • Connect with decision-makers and influencers to advocate for policy changes and implementation. • Showcase projects, case studies, and best practices in urban planning and development. • Engage with civil society organizations to collaborate on community-based initiatives.

SMA	Target Audience	Objectives
<p>YouTube</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy makers, public administration, EU institutions • Business & industry: employers • Workers • Researchers and academia • Business and industry: urban planners, real estate agents, architects • Civil society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce informative and visually engaging videos on R-Map's research findings and solutions. • Showcase success stories, interviews, and project highlights to inspire action and awareness. • Educate diverse audiences on the importance of sustainable regional development. • Reach a wider audience through multimedia storytelling and visual communication. • Foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders through video content.
<p>BlueSky</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers, public administration, EU institutions • Researchers and academia • Civil society and community-based organisations • Digital communication professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote R-Map's research findings and updates on a platform aligned with transparency and ethical communication values. • Engage with communities interested in decentralised governance and digital rights. • Support inclusive dialogue around remote work, urban-rural dynamics and regional policy. • Complement outreach efforts on other platforms by offering an alternative, community-driven communication space. • Strengthen the project's online presence in emerging, values-driven digital environments.

The management and operation of SMAs are overseen by WR, with active engagement and support expected from consortium partners. Partners are encouraged to:

- **Become Followers:** Actively engage by following or liking R-Map's social media profiles.
- **Promote in Networks:** Share and promote R-Map's SMAs within their respective networks.
- **Suggest Connections:** Provide recommendations for relevant profiles that R-Map's should connect with to expand its reach.
- **Share Content:** Actively share interesting articles, news and updates related to R-Map's goals and achievements.
- **Promote Own Content:** Boost the visibility of R-Map by promoting posts and news through the SMAs of their own organizations.

Facebook

R-Map's Facebook page, established in M1, serves as a dedicated hub for project updates and a space for engaging with our broader community. The page is regularly updated with posts that include project news,

milestones, promotional material, event participation and developments relevant to remote working arrangements and regional transformation in Europe. Posts vary in format – including visuals, text and video –are tailored to maintain a consistent tone and visual identity across all content.

Figure 34. Screenshot of R-Map's Facebook page

Facebook has shown moderate but meaningful engagement, particularly in reaching a broader and more diverse audience that includes the general public. While not as targeted as LinkedIn in terms of professional outreach, it remains a valuable platform for increasing general awareness of the project, especially through accessible, visual, and story-driven content that highlights the societal relevance of R-Map beyond academic and policy audiences.

Figure 35. Facebook's Lowest Engagement Posts

Within this context, a recent campaign introducing the **Advisory Board Members** presented mixed engagement results. While some posts attracted significant interaction, others received lower levels of engagement. Posts featuring members who are well-known industry thought leaders or who maintain large

professional networks generated the highest levels of interaction, whereas profiles of less familiar individuals saw lower engagement. For future campaigns of this nature, we plan to enhance storytelling, use consistent and engaging visuals, and provide more background on each individual’s contribution to the project to create stronger audience connection and interest.

As of April 2025, the page has published 46 posts and grown its online community to 50 followers, while gaining 29 page likes. These posts have generated **4,057 impressions**, while total **page visits reached 994**. The Facebook page is monitored through Google Analytics and Metricool where engagement and reach are continuously tracked to improve future campaigns.

In addition to sharing project updates, the Facebook page is used to:

- Disseminate developments and results of the project (e.g., reports, deliverables, key events)
- Foster discussion around R-Map’s key themes such as the urban-rural divide and remote work
- Share relevant external content from the EU policy and research landscape
- Link with other relevant pages and communities
- Promote cross-platform traffic by redirecting users to the R-Map website

This channel supports R-Map’s overall digital presence and provides a steady way to share updates with a range of interested audiences, particularly those looking for quick project highlights and entry points to learn more.

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn platform was chosen to reach a more professional audience, with the profile established in **M1** R-Map partners are expected to support the project’s LinkedIn profile, inviting followers and participating in professional discussions. The LinkedIn page takes an institutional approach, fostering expert conversations on shared interests. Metrics and insights from LinkedIn will be used to assess project performance.

Figure 36. Screenshots of R-Map's LinkedIn Page

As a platform naturally oriented toward professionals, LinkedIn aligns well with the project's target audiences such as researchers, policymakers, and academic institutions, making it an effective channel for sharing research updates, project milestones, and relevant news. Its professional nature also supports the dissemination of more in-depth or technical content, which tends to perform better with engaged, subject-specific communities. This indicates that continuing to invest in and strategically grow our LinkedIn presence will be beneficial for reaching and engaging our core stakeholders.

While overall LinkedIn engagement has been strong, a few posts—such as an early-stage project poll and a synergy announcement—underperformed. At that time, our follower base was smaller and less familiar with R-Map, with likely limited reach. The poll was published during our brand-building phase involving broader questions, and the synergy post followed a straightforward format. Moving forward, we aim to enhance narrative clarity, incorporate more engaging visual content, and tailor messaging and calls to action to better align with the preferences and expectations of LinkedIn’s professional community.

Figure 37. LinkedIn's Lowest Engagement Posts

X (Former Twitter)

The R-Map X account (formerly Twitter) was set up early in the project as part of the broader strategy to ensure presence across key social media platforms. It serves as an additional outlet to share project updates, connect with relevant initiatives and monitor sector-related discussions. While activity on this channel has been more selective, the account still offers potential for fostering visibility and engaging with audiences already active on the platform. Its role remains complementary to the project’s primary channels, particularly LinkedIn and Facebook.

Figure 38. Screenshot of R-Maps X account

Following partner recommendations and in light of practical and strategic considerations, we decided to remain inactive in the project’s **X account** (previous Twitter). First, access to in-depth analytics and basic performance insights now requires a paid subscription, which limited our ability to evaluate impact effectively and adjust our strategy. Additionally, we observed a noticeable decline in engagement and reach over time - due to external factors beyond our control- making it a less effective platform for communicating with our target audiences. As a result, we have chosen to focus our efforts on channels that offer stronger performance, better alignment with our audience, and more transparent analytics tools, such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and BlueSky.

Figure 39. X's Lowest Engagement Posts

Additionally, several posts particularly those related to the Advisory Board introduction campaign, received limited interaction, which may be due to factors such as the niche nature of the content, and the audience's emerging familiarity with the featured members. This contributed to the decision to prioritize platforms where engagement and reach better align with our communication objectives.

YouTube

The R-Map YouTube channel serves as a space to enhance the project's visibility through video-based communication. The first promotional video, released in Month 6, was published on the channel to introduce the project's vision and raise awareness among a broader audience. It was also shared across all R-Map social media platforms to maximise its reach.

The channel is dedicated to showcasing R-Map's key actions and outcomes, offering visual storytelling to complement written content. Its long-term goal is to contribute to a growing network of EU-funded projects by engaging with similar channels and expanding its reach within the online community.

Figure 40. Screenshot of R-Map's YouTube channel

As of Month 15, the channel has 49 subscribers and has gathered 349 views, marking a modest but steady start for building a visual identity for the project.

Bluesky

Bluesky was added to R-Map's social media presence in March 2025, reflecting the project's effort to stay aligned with evolving digital communication trends and the EU's commitment to transparency and decentralisation. While still in its early stages, the channel is used to cross-promote key updates and connect with emerging audiences interested in open dialogue around regional development and remote work.

Figure 41. Screenshot of R-Map's Bluesky account

BlueSky, currently records modest engagement levels largely because the platform is still new and our follower base is in its infancy. However, BlueSky is an emerging and increasingly promising channel, gaining traction and generating growing interest among key digital communities. As such, establishing an early presence offers strategic long-term value. In some cases, posts may have also been published during periods of lower audience activity, which further contributed to reduced visibility and interaction.

Figure 42. BlueSky's Lowest Engagement Post

For example, a recent post showcasing the synergy between R-Map and another Horizon Europe project saw limited reach, likely reflecting audience unfamiliarity with both initiatives and a lack of contextual framing. To enhance engagement in future posts of this kind, we consider providing a clearer explanation of the collaboration's purpose and value, schedule content to coincide with peak audience activity and actively encourage cross-promotion through partner networks.

5.2.3.1 Optimising social media performance for stronger audience engagement

In the previous section, we identified specific posts with low engagement levels across all dissemination and communication platforms. Examples include posts from the Advisory Board introduction campaign, a poll conducted on LinkedIn, and a post announcing project synergies. We have analysed several factors that likely contributed to their underperformance:

- **Early-stage visibility:** Some posts were published during early project stages when follower numbers and audience familiarity were still limited.
- **Platform maturity:** Emerging channels (e.g. BlueSky) inherently record modest engagement as their user bases develop, making early investment strategically valuable but slower to yield high interaction.
- **Audience familiarity:** Posts on topics like inter-project synergies or Advisory Board introductions saw lower pickup, reflecting audiences' emerging awareness of these initiatives and the need for richer contextual framing.
- **Contextual clarity:** In some cases, concise storytelling around the collaboration's purpose and value will help audiences immediately grasp relevance.
- **Multimedia impact:** As the platforms evolve, integrating more dynamic visuals or data snippets will boost attractiveness and shareability.
- **Audience targeting:** Some content may not have been fully tailored to the preferences and expectations of the specific social media audiences.

To address these challenges and drive stronger, more consistent engagement, we have outlined the following potential strategic actions:

Action item	Description and implementation
Develop Organic Content Calendar	Align social and news posts with key project milestones, deliverables and major results to ensure communications remain timely, coherent and directly linked to R-Map's research news-hooks.
Enhance Storytelling	Craft clearer explanations and narrative flow, whether introducing key members, explaining inter-project synergies or unpacking findings, to deepen audience understanding and engagement.
Increase Visual Engagement	Use infographics, photos, videos and data snippets to create eye-catching content that boosts shareability and encourages interaction across platforms.
Optimise Posting Times	Analyse audience activity patterns and schedule posts during peak engagement windows to maximise visibility and impact.

<p>Targeted Communication & Success Stories</p>	<p>Tag relevant stakeholders, highlight regionally grounded success stories and showcase practical R-Map applications to amplify reach and demonstrate real-world value to local and international audiences.</p>
<p>Coordinate Media Coverage</p>	<p>Synchronise press releases, social media bursts and partner contributions around major outputs to maintain momentum, sustain public interest and optimise media pickup.</p>
<p>Case-Study Campaign</p>	<p>Launch a dedicated "Case-Study Campaign" for each regional use case. Each campaign will include important insights about why the region was selected, specific challenges being addressed, research activities or interventions taking place, and any early findings, lessons, or impact observed. The aim is to bring the use cases to life by translating complex research into accessible, region-specific stories. These campaigns will help audiences, including policymakers, local stakeholders, and the general public, understand the practical relevance of R-Map’s work and how it connects to everyday issues like digitalisation, remote work, and labour mobility</p>
<p>Leverage Industry Thought Leaders & AB Members</p>	<p>Engage Advisory Board and sector influencers to amplify key messages and press releases within their established professional networks. These individuals can play a key role in amplifying our press releases and key messages within their professional networks, particularly in sectors aligned with R-Map’s core themes</p> <p>Indicative examples of individuals to be reached including their Follower Reach, Network Scope & Audience Type):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iwo Zsapar (≥40,000 followers): His network spans remote-work professionals, HR and talent-management leaders, and digital-nomad communities. Content centers on best practices for distributed teams, AI in the future of work, and tools for remote leadership. • Goncalo Hall (≥30,000 followers): Gonçalo’s audience comprises urban planners, regional policymakers and digital-transformation specialists. He shares insights on smart-city development, territorial cohesion and the policy implications of remote-work trends. • Anna Maria Kochanska (≈20,000 followers): Anna Maria Kochanska’s expertise in developmental psychology—and her audience of researchers, graduate students and child-development professionals—offers valuable insights into how remote working arrangements affect family dynamics and child well-being. • Maya Middlemiss (≥8,500 followers): Maya’s network includes environmental and transport researchers, sustainability practitioners and rural-development NGOs. Her updates focus on the socio-economic and spatial impacts of remote work, equity in infrastructure and resilient community planning.

By taking these steps, we aim to improve the effectiveness of our social media presence, ensuring stronger engagement with our core audiences and wider dissemination of the R-Map project’s work.

5.2.4 R-Map Advisory Board Campaign

As part of R-Map’s social media strategy, a dedicated campaign was launched to introduce the members of the project’s Advisory Board to a wider audience. The aim of this campaign was to showcase the expertise supporting the project and to strengthen stakeholder trust and engagement.

A series of visually consistent social media posts were developed, each highlighting an individual Advisory Board member, their role and area of expertise. These posts were published across R-Map’s Facebook, LinkedIn and X accounts and included a direct link to the Advisory Board section of the website, where users could access more detailed information about the Board’s composition and contributions.

The campaign not only increased traffic to the website but also helped position the Advisory Board as an integral part of the project’s strategic direction. The Advisory Board page has become one of the most visited sections of the R-Map website, demonstrating the interest it generated among our audience.

This campaign reflects R-Map’s commitment to transparency and stakeholder engagement, while also contributing to the visibility of the individuals and institutions guiding the project’s progress.

Figure 43. Screenshot of posts and graphics from R-Map's AB social media campaign

5.2.5 Digital Analytics and Monitoring Tools

To effectively track and evaluate R-Map's dissemination and communication performance, a combination of digital analytics tools is used throughout the project.

Google Analytics is employed to monitor website traffic, including key indicators such as page views, user engagement, geographic reach and source of visits. This enables the team to understand how users interact with the R-Map website and optimise content delivery accordingly.

Metricool is a social media analytics and scheduling tool that allows the project team to monitor the performance of R-Map's social media channels in real time. It provides consolidated metrics on impressions, engagement (likes, shares, comments), reach and audience demographics across platforms like Facebook, LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter). The tool also supports editorial planning by enabling content scheduling and tracking post-performance.

Together, these tools provide a comprehensive picture of the project's digital footprint and audience interaction. The insights gathered help inform adjustments to the communication strategy, guide content development and ensure alignment with the project's outreach goals and KPIs.

5.2.6 Stakeholder Engagement via Social Media Channels

R-Map's social media presence continues to reflect the project's aim to reach a broad and relevant stakeholder base, with LinkedIn emerging as its strongest digital outreach tool. The audience includes a diverse mix of professionals, with strong representation from the **Professional Services** (34.94%), **Education** (16.76%), and **Government Administration** (8.73%) sectors—closely aligned with the project's key stakeholder categories such as consultants, academics, policy advisors, and public officials.

Geographically, the project has established solid outreach across various European countries, including **Greece, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Spain and Türkiye**, highlighting its ability to engage different regional contexts across the continent.

Over the reporting period, **LinkedIn recorded 42.5K impressions and 5,429 interactions across 62 posts**, confirming it as the most effective platform for engagement. The consistent post frequency and strategic content delivery helped build a follower base of **561**, with regular spikes in engagement corresponding to project milestones and events.

Although Facebook remains a secondary channel, it contributes to the project's visibility—especially for localised and event-related updates—supporting around **4K impressions** and growing to **50 followers**.

Together, these insights highlight the effectiveness of R-Map's professional-facing communication strategy, with LinkedIn serving as a reliable space for policy dialogue, stakeholder networking and amplification of project results.

The following visuals from Metricool provide an overview of the performance and reach of R-Map's social media activity during the reporting period, further supporting the insights outlined above:

Figure 44. Screenshot of Metricool report - LinkedIn page impressions

Figure 45. Screenshot of Metricool Report - Interactions of published posts on LinkedIn

Figure 46. Screenshot of Metricool report – LinkedIn followers location

Figure 47. Screenshot of Metricool report- LinkedIn community growth

Figure 48. Screenshot of Metricool report – LinkedIn followers location

5.3 Media Coverage

This section provides an overview of R-Map’s targeted, strategic approach to engage with media outlets as part of its broader communication and dissemination strategy. Media engagement plays a crucial role in raising public awareness, informing stakeholders, and supporting evidence-based dialogue on remote working arrangements (RWAs), spatial transformation, and regional development. To amplify **newsworthy** project milestones, findings and events and reach diverse audiences, the project targets both **general media outlets** (e-newspapers, news agencies, newsletters, etc.) and **niche or specialist publishers** (focused on specific sectors such as labour markets, digitalisation, etc.).

R-Map aims to ensure widespread communication of its activities and findings through a well-balanced media outreach strategy targeting a mix of general and specialist outlets. To support this effort, project partners have been invited to contribute information on relevant media platforms and communication channels from their local and regional contexts, leveraging the outlets they already access. These inputs will be compiled into two tables: one listing general media outlets, and another covering niche or specialist channels relevant to R-Map’s thematic scope. This living section will be updated as media outreach activities evolve throughout the project lifecycle.

The main objectives of this approach are:

- To ensure consistent, effective and targeted communication of R-Map’s activities, findings, and events.
- To raise awareness and stimulate evidence-based dialogue on RWAs and their socio-economic impacts among both expert and general audiences.

- Maintain a geographically balanced, multi-level (local, national, EU) media presence.

Build sustained media relationships that reinforce R-Map’s policy messages and future coverage.

The distinction between general and niche media outlets was made based on the scope of topics covered and the audience they target. Media outlets considered “general” typically address a broad range of topics such as politics, society, economy, and culture, and they are aimed at wide audiences including the general public, regional communities, or policymakers. This category includes regional newspapers, government newsletters with broad relevance to public affairs. In contrast, “niche” media outlets focus on specific sectors or disciplines, such as finance, public relations, technology, and are targeted at specialised audiences including researchers, business professionals, and other. This distinction ensures that the R-Map project can tailor its outreach strategies appropriately, leveraging general media for wide public visibility and using niche outlets for targeted engagement with expert communities and key stakeholders.

Table 6. Indicative General Media Outlets

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
University Media	U-Today	Twente (The Netherlands)	U-Today is the independent journalistic medium at the University of Twente (UT).	University community	Students, academics, researchers	Academic, research and regional insights. Useful for showcasing Use Case Scenarios that demonstrate research application and societal value.

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
Regional Newspaper	Tubantia	Twente (The Netherlands)	Tubantia is proud to be the regional news brand of the East of the country.	Regional, broad audience	General public, policymakers, local businesses	Regional socio-economic impact of RWAs. Suitable for highlighting Use Case Scenarios that showcase real-life regional applications.
Business Media	Business Insider Nederland	Amsterdam (The Netherlands)	Business Insider Nederland is an online audio and video media focusing on entrepreneurship, careers, personal finance, and technology.	National	General public, policymakers, business professionals, entrepreneurs, local businesses	Relevant for dissemination of innovation, economic impact, and business-focused results of the R-Map project. Supports outreach to stakeholders in regional development, policy, and the private sector.

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
E-Newspaper	Voria.gr	Thessaloniki (Greece)	An e-newspaper featuring a wide range of categories, including news from the Macedonia region, Greece, economics, business, and more.	Regional, broad audience	General public, policymakers, local businesses, workers	Regional news, business, social impacts. Suitable for showcasing Greek Use Case Scenarios with local impact.
E-Newspaper	Makedonia	Thessaloniki (Greece)	The goal of e-makedonia.gr is to deliver detailed and comprehensive information to its readers, offering a carefully curated blend of news, articles, analysis, and opinions.	Regional, broad audience	General public, policymakers, local businesses, workers	Detailed regional news and analysis. Useful for illustrating Use Case Scenarios that affect local communities or sectors.
E-Newspaper	The Opinion	Thessaloniki (Greece)	Theopinion.gr is a news website based in Thessaloniki. It includes categories like Politics, Economics, Society, Local News, Sports, and many more.	Regional, broad audience	General public, policymakers, local businesses, workers	Socioeconomic and political insights. Good platform for Use Case Scenarios that relate to real-life impacts on society or policy.

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
Online News Channel	IN	Athens (Greece)	It is an online news channel, under the umbrella of "Alter Ego Media A.E.", and it includes categories like science, sports, economics, etc.	National	General public, science & economics audiences, workers	Science, economics related to RWAs. Use Case Scenarios can be included if framed around national or scientific impact.
News Agency	ATHENS-MACEDO NIAN NEWS AGENCY	Cyprus	The Athens News Agency - Macedonian Press Agency (ANA-MPA) has a presence in the media sector that extends for more than a century. The ANA-MPA produces, collects, edits and disseminates domestic and international news items and photographs, as well as radio and television material for distribution to media outlets in Greece, Cyprus, numerous third countries and the Greek diaspora.	National/International	General public, policymakers, local businesses, workers	Broad media distribution

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
Local Media	Stonisi	Lesvos (Greece)	A local news media outlet based on the island of Lesvos, Greece, covering a wide range of categories including society, economy, sports, and more.	Local	General public, policymakers, local businesses, workers	Local community impact of RWAs. Use Case Scenarios can be included showing local impact.
Council Newsletter	Surrey County Council Newsletter	Surrey (UK)	Local government newsletter with policymaker audience.	Local Government	Local policymakers, civil servants	Policy influence at local level
Professional Network (Newsletter)	METREX Newsletter	Belgium / Europe-wide	METREX is a network of over 50 metropolitan regions and areas in Europe.	Policymakers, planners	Urban planners, policymakers	Regional urban & planning policy
News Website	Euronews	Pan-European	Euronews is an international news media, providing news with a European perspective to a worldwide audience both on TV and digital platforms.	Policymakers	General public, policymakers, local businesses, workers	Strong EU policy and innovation focus

Table 7. Indicative Niche Media Outlets

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Estimated Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
Financial News Site	Reporteur	Athens (Greece)	News website specializing in financial and stock market news	Specialized (finance)	Digital nomads, remote worker communities, industry associations, employers' unions, SMEs, business decision-makers, NGOs, citizens	Economic and financial impacts of RWAs
Press Portal	Pressefeurer.at	Austria	Austrian press portal focused on business releases and education industry news	Industry-specific	Businesses, educators, academics	Business and academic communication
Press Release Site	OpenPR.de	Germany	They are one of the leading German press portals with over 1 million published press releases and more than 200,000 authors for diverse sectors including science and education.	Wide (industry & public)	Industry stakeholders, businesses, academics	Publicising scientific & business info

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Estimated Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
Digital Communication	Pressbox	Germany	They enable high-quality digital enterprise communication in the B2B area with a focus on the areas of technology and industry and offer new possibilities to generate effective and measurable attention to topics.	B2B Industry	Industry stakeholders, businesses, digital nomads, SMEs, business decision-makers	Platform focused on technology, R&D, and medical tech communications
Academic Journal	Frontier today	Austria	It is an independent, non-partisan, and non-governmental initiative launched online since 2018 in Vienna (Austria), aspiring to make favorable changes in the publishing and education industry in business studies.	Research and Academic, Business	Researchers, students, academics, businesses	Business sustainability and research

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Estimated Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
PR Agency	Lobby PR	Turkey	Lobby PR is one of Turkey's first PR agencies with more than 30 years of experience.	Specialized (PR clients)	Industry, local businesses, digital nomads, SMEs, business decision-makers	Communications and awareness campaigns

The media outlets presented in both tables above represent an indicative list based on input from consortium partners, their existing networks, and their regional communication channels. This selection reflects current opportunities for dissemination and engagement, aligned with the early phases of the R-Map project. As the project progresses and new outputs, events, and policy dialogues are developed, we anticipate expanding this list to include additional media channels both locally and internationally, ensuring broader outreach and more targeted communication in response to evolving project needs and stakeholder interests.

To enhance the visibility and outreach of the second R-Map press release, a variety of communication channels were utilised, including online platforms, online news, and institutional platforms. These channels were selected to ensure broad and balanced coverage across different stakeholder groups. The following table provides an overview of the main outlets and platforms that supported the dissemination efforts.

Table 8. Media and Communication Channels Contacted for Dissemination of R-Map’s Second Press Release (M15)

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Estimated Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
Online Publication	Tech.eu	London (UK)	Tech.eu is the premier online publication dedicated to the growing European technology ecosystem(s), delivering a range of editorial products with a clear focus on curated news, actionable information and educational interviews with movers and shakers from across Europe	European tech community	Researchers, Policy Makers, Business	Shares curated news and interviews on European tech ecosystems

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Estimated Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
Online Platform	Smart Cities World	London (UK)	SmartCitiesWorld is a world-leading platform for sharing ideas and case studies to solve urban challenges that enable us to live in more resilient, sustainable, safe, and prosperous environments.	Global urban professionals	Urban Experts, Policy Makers	Focuses on urban resilience, sustainability, and innovation
Network Publication	EuroCITIES	Brussels (Belgium)	The largest network of European cities. They count over 200 large cities among their membership, representing more than 150 million people across 38 countries, from within and outside the European Union.	National / International	Policy Makers, Urban Experts	Largest network of European cities influencing urban policy
Online News Site	Euobserver	Brussels (Belgium)	It is the premier, member-supported, non-profit news site on EU affairs.	EU affairs followers	Policy Makers, Researchers	Premier news source on EU affairs
EU Project Portal	Cordis	Brussels (Belgium)	The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) is the European Commission's primary source for the results of projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation.	EU research community	Policy Makers, Researchers	Primary source for EU-funded research results

Type of Outlet	Media Outlet Name	Country/Region covered	Short description	Estimated Audience Reach	Target Groups	Relevance to Project
EU Magazine	Horizon - The EU Research & Innovation Magazine	Brussels (Belgium)	Magazine covering EU research and innovation news, published by the European Commission.	EU research community	Policy Makers, Researchers	Official publication from DG Research & Innovation
News Website	WITNews	Pan-European	WIT News is your premier destination for European research and innovation news, born from a vision to bridge the gap between groundbreaking discoveries and public understanding.	Innovation community	General public, policymakers, businesses, researchers	Strong innovation and research focus, as well as reports on research results and innovative technologies
Institutional Bulletin	European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) Bulletin	Brussels (Belgium)	Provides opinions and viewpoints on EU issues from socio-economic representatives.	Socio-economic stakeholders	Policy Makers, Civil Society	Platform for socio-occupational interest groups

The listed media channels were contacted to explore opportunities for publishing or promoting R-Map’s second press release. The goal was to increase broader awareness of the project’s objectives, particularly the development of its data-driven visualisation platform. Among them, **WIT News** has already proceeded with the publication of the press release. Engagement with the remaining outlets helped to establish initial lines of communication, which are considered an important first step toward fostering ongoing relationships with relevant media actors. These initial interactions are viewed as a valuable first step in building relationships with relevant media actors. The project team intends to maintain these connections and continue exploring collaboration opportunities as new content, milestones, and results emerge over the course of the project.

5.3.1 Media Coverage Achieved

Throughout the R-Map project's timeline, all consortium partners are encouraged to generate press and media releases, contribute articles to mainstream media, participate in TV or radio presentations, or engage with

other media outlets. The primary objective of these efforts is to enhance the project's visibility and public recognition, extending its reach to stakeholders beyond the consortium. Each partner is responsible for identifying suitable publishing opportunities and taking necessary actions to ensure the effective promotion of the project's assets and results.

So far, two press releases have been published as part of the project's communication efforts:

1. **The Kick-Off Press Release**, announcing the launch of the R-Map project and its overarching objectives. It was also featured on [WITNEWS](#) (see Table 8), providing pan-European reach and contributing to broader media coverage during the early project phase.

Figure 49. R-Map's Kick-Off Press Release featured on the WITNEWS website

2. **The R-MAP Platform Press Release**, which communicated the development of the R-Map visualisation platform architecture and its significance for policymakers and stakeholders. The second press release for our project has been uploaded to the project [website](#) and distributed through external channels to increase visibility. Similar to the first release, it has also been published on the [WITNEWS website](#) and shared across its social media platforms (see Table 8), including [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#), providing pan-European reach

Figure 50. R-Map's Second Press Release featured on the WITNEWS website

3. **R-Map's Coordinator, Professor Efstratios Stylianidis, was featured in an [interview](#) with Dnews.gr (also known as Dikaiologitika.gr), a widely read Greek online news platform that covers a broad range of topics including politics, the economy, health, technology, and current affairs. In the interview, Professor Stylianidis presented the goals and significance of the R-Map project, highlighting its potential impact on regional development and policymaking. The feature boosted public awareness and delivered strong local visibility in the city tied to one of the use cases of the project, reaching a wider audience beyond the academic and professional communities.**

Figure 51. R-Map's Coordinator, Professor Efstratios Stylianidis Interview in Dnews.gr

4. **The R-Map project was recently featured on Andy Sto’s blog** in an [article](#) exploring how remote and hybrid work are reshaping living and working patterns across Europe. This article highlights R-Map’s survey findings, its innovative framework for assessing regional impacts, and its upcoming interactive platform designed to support evidence-based policymaking. The blog targets a pan-European / international niche audience of remote-work and digital-nomad professionals, offering targeted, sector-specific visibility, primarily among professionals and enthusiasts following remote/hybrid work trends and regional development in Europe.

Figure 52. R-Map Article on ANDY STO Blog

While there is no specified minimum for press and media engagement activities, a record of all published materials is maintained through the Dissemination Reporting Template (Annex IV), based on actual progress.

5.4 Breaking News Communication Workflow

To ensure timely and targeted dissemination of key project developments, we have implemented a structured breaking-news workflow. This process is designed to communicate major milestones, outputs, or events in a rapid and coordinated manner. The process includes the following steps:

- Key milestones:
The workflow begins whenever significant project activities or results occurs, including publication of deliverables, major project meetings, key findings, or policy-relevant outputs.
 - **Timeline:** The workflow should start within 1–2 working days of the activity, milestone, or event, depending on the nature of the activity.
- Content Development (responsible TL):
A short summary (150–300 words) is drafted by the TL leading the key development.
 - **Timeline:** The draft summary should ideally be submitted within 3-5 working days from the start of the workflow. This allows sufficient time for the TL to reflect on the development and ensure the messaging is accurate, relevant, and engaging, while keeping the overall dissemination process timely.
- Editing, Reviewing and adaptation (Dissemination Manager)
The summary is reviewed internally and adapted for different formats and audiences.
 - **Timeline:** The review and finalisation to be completed within 2–3 working days after receiving the draft.
- Multi-Channel Dissemination (Dissemination Manager):
The content is disseminated through:
 - ◆ The project website (under the “News” section)
 - ◆ Bi-annual newsletters
 - ◆ Project social media accounts (LinkedIn, Facebook, BlueSky, etc.), as well as reposts shared by partners on their respective social media channels.
 - ◆ Partner organisation communication channels (websites, newsletters)
 - ◆ Media Outlets (more information in chapter 5.3 Media Coverage)
 - **Timeline:** Dissemination should take place within 1–2 working days after the content is finalised.
- Monitoring & Feedback (Dissemination Manager):
Engagement data (e.g. page visits, comments, shares / re-posts, clicks) is collected and fed into the project’s KPI dashboard to assess the effectiveness of dissemination activities and inform future content planning.
 - **Timeline:** Initial data review to be conducted within 1 week of dissemination, as monitoring continues on an ongoing basis.

5.5 Events

5.5.1 R-Map’s Internal events and conferences

As part of the R-Map project, a number of events are planned to support the project’s objectives and promote its outcomes. These events are defined in the Grant Agreement and form an integral part of the project’s overall strategy. Specifically, the following types of events are scheduled throughout the project’s duration:

Table 9. R-Map's internal events

Event	WP, Task, Responsible partner	Short description	Approx. Date
1 Full Day Physical Model Validation Workshop (Netherlands)	WP2, T.2.1, UT	The technical workshops aim to consolidate insights from WP1, establishing a shared understanding of the urban-rural divide within R-Map's context. They focus on defining key dimensions and factors affected by RWAs across regions, facilitating expert assessment and semi-quantification to inform project strategies.	M10 <i>Completed</i>
3-5 Online technical workshops	WP2, T.2.1, UT	The technical workshops aim to consolidate insights from WP1, establishing a shared understanding of the urban-rural divide within R-Map's context. They focus on defining key dimensions and factors affected by RWAs across regions, facilitating expert assessment and semi-quantification to inform project strategies.	M5 <i>Completed</i>
1 Technical Workshop R-Map visualization platform	WP3, T3.1, ARX.NET	The workshop will be held between ARX.NET, UT, AUTH, SEERC, KU, SURREY, UB, METREX and Q-PLAN in order to conclude on the most useful types of data to be visualised through the R-Map platform along with their format.	M11 <i>Completed</i>
1 Dedicated digital workshop	WP3, T3.1, ARX.NET	The dedicated workshop aims to discuss and improve the platform's architecture with the help of the Advisory Board	M11 <i>Completed</i>
Regional Delphi Workshops	WP4, T.4.2, Q-PLAN	Aims to implement the Delphi method for the qualitative forecasting	M26
Meeting with sister projects	WP5, T5.3, Q-PLAN	A half-a-day (virtual) cluster meeting and/or policy roundtable with the sister projects will be organized.	M26
6 Regional Policy (co-creation) Workshops	WP4, T.4.3, UB	The 6 policy workshops will be held physically and will be hosted by the local partners UT, AUTH, KU, SURREY, RIM and UB in their regions in order to facilitate collaborative discussions and decision-making among stakeholders to address regional challenges arising from RWAs.	M27-M31

Event	WP, Task, Responsible partner	Short description	Approx. Date
6 Cross Regional Dialogues	WP4, T.4.4, WR	The cross-regional dialogues aim to present and discuss the scenarios and their impacts, with each session focusing on the results of a specific use case	M31-M35
Policy Roundtable	WP5, T.5.4, METREX	Aims to foster discussions on how taxation, social security, labour, economic and other relevant regulatory and social aspects could or should change in order to keep pace with the remote working arrangement and their effects (and trade-offs).	M30-M34
Final Conference	WP5, T.5.1, WR	Final Conference aims at showcasing research findings, policy insights and fostering collaborative discussions on remote work's impact and urban-rural dynamics. (The event will be combined with a Policy Roundtable).	M36

Full-Day Physical Model Validation Workshop (Netherlands)

As part of WP2 (Task 2.1), the R-Map consortium held a full-day in-person technical workshop in the Netherlands. This session brought together project partners and experts to consolidate findings from WP1 and validate the initial structure of the R-Map model. Through collaborative discussions, participants identified the most critical dimensions of the urban-rural divide and assessed the socio-spatial factors influenced by remote working arrangements (RWAs). The workshop supported the semi-quantification process and helped align perspectives across disciplines, laying a strong foundation for the project's modelling work.

Series of Online Technical Workshops

Later in the project, a series of 4 online technical workshops was organised under WP2 (Task 2.1) to build a shared understanding of the urban-rural divide across Europe. These sessions served as a space to assess preliminary insights from WP1 and begin defining the main variables and regional factors influenced by RWAs. The virtual format allowed broad partner participation and enabled initial semi-quantitative assessments to be made collaboratively. These discussions directly informed the development of the modelling framework.

Technical Workshop on the R-Map Visualisation Platform

Conducted under WP3 (Task 3.1), this **dedicated workshop** brought together ARX.NET and key technical partners (UT, AUTh, SEERC, KU Leuven, University of Surrey, University of Barcelona, METREX, and Q-PLAN, UB) to align on the **types of data to be visualised** through the R-Map platform. Discussions focused on identifying the most policy-relevant data outputs and agreeing on the formats and structures needed to ensure usability for different stakeholder groups. This session was a crucial milestone toward shaping the platform's user experience and ensuring clarity in how project findings are presented.

Dedicated Digital Workshop with the Advisory Board

Also under WP3 (Task 3.1), a **targeted digital workshop** was held to discuss the architectural design of the R-Map platform. This session was organised with the participation of **Advisory Board members**, offering valuable external feedback and strategic input. The discussion helped refine key components of the platform, particularly in terms of usability, navigation and relevance to policy audiences. Insights from this session were integrated into the ongoing development process to ensure the platform meets both user expectations and communication goals.

A total of 49 participants attended the internal events organised so far, including consortium members, external contributors and Advisory Board members, reflecting a strong level of engagement across the project's key stakeholder groups.

5.5.2 External events and conferences

The participation of R-Map consortium partners in external events, conferences, and forums plays a key role in enhancing the project's visibility and expanding its outreach beyond the immediate consortium. These occasions offer valuable opportunities to engage with a diverse and multidisciplinary audience, share R-Map's approach and build connections with stakeholders from policy, academia and practice.

Throughout the project's duration, partners have taken part in a number of high-level events with the aim to:

- Present the concept, methodology and objectives of R-Map
- Stay informed about the latest developments and debates around remote work and regional development
- Share emerging insights and findings from the project
- Develop relationships with relevant stakeholders and networks
- Promote ongoing activities and upcoming results
- Raise awareness of R-Map's relevance to both policy and practice

To ensure consistency and coherence in the project's public image, all partners are encouraged to use the official R-Map dissemination materials, including the leaflet, poster and presentation templates. All visuals are aligned with the project's visual identity, including consistent use of colours, fonts and the official logo. Presentations delivered at external events should follow the project templates and partners are invited to notify the communication team ahead of their participation to support coordination and visibility.

So far, the R-Map project participated in the following external events and conferences:

- 2nd Open-Air Cities International Conference – Athens, Greece
- 6th International Conference on Changing Cities – Rhodes Island, Greece

- IGFI Seminar, University of Muenster – Germany
- International Research Society for Public Management (IRSPM) Conference – Bologna, Italy
- Academy of Management Conference: Innovation for the Future – Online
- AMJ Paper Development Workshop – Switzerland
- REMOTE- IT Forum: Green Transition and Remote Work – Online
- Workplace 2025: Trends Shaping the Future of Work Across Europe – Online Webinar by Studio Alliance
- WinWin4WorkLife online consortium Meeting – Online
- Occupational Health and Safety Meeting – KU University, Turkey

This participation reflects the consortium’s commitment to engaging with key actors and contributing to ongoing discourse on remote work, spatial justice and regional development across Europe. Finally, following participation in any external event, partners are kindly requested to complete the **event reporting template** (Annex II) and submit it to White Research to ensure proper documentation and tracking of dissemination activities. This process helps monitor outreach efforts and supports internal reporting requirements. Table 10 below outlines an indicative list of potential events that the R-Map team could participate in.

Table 10. R-Map external events and conferences

Event/ Conference	Short description	Link
Running Remote 2025: The Fastest Growing Conference on Flexible Work	A two-day conference that brings together hundreds of companies from around the globe to discuss the latest strategies & learn from industry leaders on flexible work, company culture, scaling, transitioning, AI and more.	link
6th annual Future of Work Europe event	A two-day event packed with fresh insights and the latest trends you need to stay ahead with all this related to the workplace, learning and talent.	link
The Future of Work Conference	An event that brings together key executives from sectors such as HR, recruitment, education, training, tech, manufacturing and supply chain, focusing on the opportunities and challenges in the workplace and the tools we need to drive transformation across the workplace.	link
8th Wellbeing at Work Summit Europe	A three-day festival that attracts senior-level HR, Reward, Wellness, Benefit and business leaders, who want to take their wellbeing and mental health strategies to the next level.	link

37th AESOP Annual Congress	<p>The 37th AESOP Congress, "<i>Planning as a Transformative Action in an Age of Planetary Crisis</i>," in Istanbul seeks to address these interconnected challenges through the lens of spatial justice, ethics and care. The event aims to foster a dialogue on how planning can become a vehicle for addressing not only environmental crises but also the socio-spatial inequalities that exist within cities and regions.</p>	link
EURA 2025 Annual Conference	<p>The European Urban Research Association (EURA) conference focuses on urban research and practice, addressing topics such as spatial inequalities, governance, and sustainable development. The theme of 2025 conference is "Creating healthy and sustainable cities".</p>	link
2025 RSA Annual Conference - Navigating Regional Transformation	<p>A four-day conference brings together academics and policymakers to exchange news, views and research findings from the fields of regional studies and science, regional and economic development, policy and planning.</p>	link
International Research Society of Public Management (IRSPM)	<p>The IRSPM develops and supports research about public management and public policy implementation amongst the international research community. It aims to facilitate the creation and dissemination of new knowledge and understanding across this community and into policy and practice. The 2026 conference will focus on the theme: "Beyond Boundaries: Wellbeing, Innovation and the Future of Public Management"</p>	link
European Group of Public Administration (EGPA)	<p>The EGPA facilitates dialogue between the European Commission and Member States on public administration and governance challenges. Representatives from each Member State participate, focusing on horizontal issues, policy coordination, and modernisation.</p>	link

5.6 Publications

5.6.1 Scientific Publications

Scientific publications play a pivotal role in disseminating R-Map's findings and insights to academic, research, and industrial communities. By sharing project outcomes through peer-reviewed journals, R-Map aims to foster lasting impact and empower researchers and stakeholders to incorporate these discoveries into their endeavours. Throughout the project, academic partners are actively involved in producing high-quality publications that address R-Map's core themes, such as remote working arrangements, urban-rural dynamics, and regional policy development. These publications support the project's aim of strengthening the research base on remote work's spatial, social and economic implications.

As of Month 15, two publications are in preparation. While the final journal selection is pending, the abstracts and working titles are provided below:

Paper #1: The Urban-Rural Divide in Remote Work: Regional Attitudes, Challenges, and Opportunities

This study explores the impacts of remote work on individuals in urban and rural regions across various employment sectors, focusing on key dimensions such as flexibility, benefits, adaptability, preferences, career development, well-being, challenges, and productivity. Remote work could theoretically decentralize economic activity, curb rural-to-urban migration, and promote balanced regional development. However, empirical evidence on its effectiveness, especially regarding urban and rural differences, remains limited.

Drawing on data from a global survey of 20,013 participants collected via Prolific between July and August 2024, the study uses Bayesian independent t-tests and ANCOVA to reveal nuanced differences in remote work experiences between urban and rural workers. The findings underscore the need for inclusive remote work policies that ensure equitable access to teleworkable jobs, digital infrastructure, and professional development opportunities—particularly for rural populations.

Paper #2: Remote Working in Urban and Rural Areas Across Europe

This data descriptor presents the collected data on remote work among urban and rural workers, emphasizing differences in perceived flexibility, adaptability, preferences, career impacts, well-being and productivity. The dataset, drawn from 20,013 participants with European nationality, was collected via Prolific between July and August 2024.

The data is intended to support not only this analysis but also future research and policy development on remote work. Its granularity on socio-economic indicators makes it valuable for urban planners, researchers, and policymakers seeking to understand and address urban-rural disparities through informed strategies and sustainable remote working practices.

The following is a list of pre-selected journals where R-Map publications may be submitted:

Table 11. Indicative list of pre-selected journals for R-Map publications

Journal	Impact Factor
International Journal on Working Conditions	1.98
Journal of Business Research	10.969
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	10.88
Travel Behaviour and Society	5.85
Sustainability Journal (section of Sustainable Urban and Rural Development)	3.889
Work, Employment and Society	4.249
Journal of Transport & Health	3.613
Journal of Transport and Geography	5.899
Journal of Regional Science	2.589
Urban Studies	3.764

Journal	Impact Factor
Environmental Science and Policy	4.128
Public Administration Review	8.3
Public Management Review	4.9
Public Money and Management Review	4.221

6. Roles and responsibilities

In the R-MAP project, each consortium member has played a pivotal role in communication activities to meet the goals and objectives outlined in the D&C plan, ensuring optimal project functionality. Partner participation and contributions have directly influenced the project's development, including activities, outcomes and overall progress, which have been communicated through dissemination efforts and various communication tools.

Partners are expected to continue to actively contribute to the project's online presence, providing suitable material for social media and website posts and promoting these posts to expand the project's followership. Additionally, partners are encouraged to support broader project promotion by participating in relevant events and conferences and contributing to online and offline publications.

At the end of each project month, all partners have been reminded to update the Dissemination Reporting template, available online in the project's repository (Annex IV), detailing the main dissemination and communication actions undertaken within the month (if any). Examples of dissemination activities include event organization, participation, interviews, communication campaigns, publishing, training and more.

Responsibilities have been allocated to determine who will execute the DCP. The dissemination and communication strategy's implementation remains a collective effort among all consortium partners. The dissemination and communication manager (WR) continues to oversee the activities' implementation and progress toward achieving DCP objectives. Partners' contributions naturally align with project development, involving stakeholder engagement, communication and the promotion of project assets.

All partners are required to report their dissemination and communication activities to the dissemination manager, following the outlined process in the respective chapter. All partners' responsibilities and expected activities are summarised in the following table:

Table 12. Partners' responsibilities.

Activity	Partner's responsibility
Online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide content for the website, SMAs and the newsletter. The goals are to ensure a constant flow of content around the project's actions and keep our online presence active and useful for the relevant stakeholders. • Promote the website, SMAs and the newsletter through their network. • Inform the dissemination manager about relevant events or news in the sector that could be used for content creation.

Activity	Partner's responsibility
Offline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organise events and raise awareness on the project results main topics. Disseminate the promotional material of the project (leaflet, poster, etc) All partners through their participation in the external events and conferences and through publications for online/offline sources (website, newspapers, magazines, etc.) should ensure the widest exposure and dissemination of the project.
Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All partners must report the carried-out dissemination and communication activities to the dissemination manager (WR). All partners must also report their synergies with other relevant projects, networks, initiatives, and research efforts to the clustering task leader (Q-PLAN). More information for the process will follow in the respective chapter.

7. Networks and Synergies

The establishment of synergies and coordination of our actions with relevant complementary projects, initiatives, and networks, leveraging the already established collaborations and extensive networks of our partners, is the goal of T5.3 *“Clustering and cooperation with relevant projects, networks and initiatives”*. The synergies leader (Q-PLAN) coordinates the cooperation with relevant projects, initiatives, and networks to establish synergies and exchange knowledge with them. Collaborations with relevant initiatives and projects refer to joint dissemination activities, mutual promotion, knowledge exchange, participation in other projects' events, expert engagement, etc.

This section presents the synergy and cooperation activities, with the objective of establishing two-way communication pathways and joint communication, dissemination, and other collaboration activities with selected projects, initiatives and networks at either the international or national level, in order to:

- Promote each other's activities and events, fostering participation.
- Align with, benefit from, and provide input to other relevant projects, initiatives, and networks.
- Foster information and knowledge exchange between projects, initiatives, and networks.

To fulfil the above objectives, the synergies leader provided partners with guidelines including the main steps to develop and implement the synergetic and cooperation activities, outlining the partners' roles and responsibilities, and explaining how to report information covering the synergies they establish. Throughout the duration of the project, all consortium partners should: (i) update their suggestions for potential synergies with relevant initiatives and (ii) report their synergetic activities. To that end, a dedicated reporting excel file (see also Annex V) has been designed and shared by Q-PLAN, including the following sheets:

- “Relevant Initiatives” sheet:** Potential candidate initiatives for synergies identified by partners and suggested synergetic actions
- “Clustering” sheet:** All the synergetic activities carried out by the partners (in which partners participated or organised).
- “X Initiative's Info” sheet:** Information on the projects the partners synergised with, lists of potential future synergetic actions with the projects they clustered and current status of their collaboration.

- **“KPI” sheet:** The number of projects, networks, initiatives and research efforts that R-Map has established synergies with (see Table 13).

Through the guidelines, a number of strategic steps have been defined to develop and implement the synergy and cooperation activities, namely:

- **Mapping and screening of relevant projects, initiatives, and networks:** All project partners suggested projects, networks, initiatives, and research efforts (55 suggestions up until M15). Based on the information gathered, Q-PLAN screened the suggestions and prioritised the ones to be approached based on criteria such as having a relevant focus with R-Map, being projects funded by the same call, being EU-wide initiatives, being active/ on-going projects, networks, initiatives and research efforts, being an existing or previous collaboration with one of the project partners.
- **Establishment of two-way communication pathways with selected projects, initiatives, and networks:** including (i) the sister projects of R-Map namely **REMAKING** and **WinWin4WorkLife** of HORIZON-CL2-2023-TRANSFORMATIONS-01 call topic, which were first approached by the PC (after being introduced by the PO) and then brought in contact with the synergies leader; and (ii) other relevant projects or initiatives, at either European or local level. Q-PLAN scheduled dedicated meetings with each project to discuss potential synergies.
- **Identification of potential synergies:** All partners suggested potential collaboration actions for the projects, initiatives and networks they suggested. Regarding Sister Projects, Q-PLAN and the PC came up with a list of suggestions for collaborative actions, which were discussed among the three projects in dedicated meetings to commonly agree on potential synergetic actions and activities.
- **Cooperation for the implementation of joint actions:** Bilateral and trilateral meetings with the sister projects took place to further discuss and identify opportunities for collaboration and follow up on the implementation of specific joint actions. Regarding other initiatives, projects and networks, Q-PLAN conducted a number of initiatives at the EU-level and partners approached initiatives with local character (mainly in light of the WP1 interviews), and discussed with them on potential common actions and activities. In total, R-Map managed to deploy around 20 synergetic actions and activities, with 9 projects.

Up until the elaboration of the current report, R-Map has achieved synergies with the following projects and initiatives:

Table 13. List of projects and initiatives with which R-Map has established Synergies

No	Acronym	Short description
1	<u>REMAKING</u> (sister project)	REMAKING aims to deliver a policy-oriented framework reflecting the new and multi-faceted realities of remote working, facilitating policymakers to adopt place-based policies balancing the opportunities and risks of remote working and sharing practices to foster mutual learning on remote working in the novel scenario of megatrends and shocks.

No	Acronym	Short description
2	<u>WinWin4WorkLife</u> (sister project)	WinWin4WorkLife seeks to foster sustainable remote working arrangements (RWA) in Europe by integrating employer and employee perspectives to promote a healthy, inclusive and sustainable work-life balance across various urban, rural, and cross-border settings.
3	<u>MOBI-TWIN</u>	MOBI-TWIN is an EU-funded project dedicated to unravelling the dynamics of spatial mobility and its significant impact on European Union regions. The project aims to understand the intricate patterns of mobility and leverage this knowledge to foster regional prosperity.
4	<u>REMOTE-IT</u>	REMOTE-IT network is funded by the URBACT program and deals with remote working and green transition, tackling the new challenges cities are experiencing connected to the future of work.
5	<u>TİSK</u>	Turkish Employer Union Confederation. It is the sole umbrella organisation authorised to represent Turkish employers in industrial relations nationally and internationally.
6	<u>Future of Work</u>	The Future of Work Research Centre leads innovative interdisciplinary research on evolving work relationships and the factors driving these changes. Its work focuses on understanding the impact of these shifts on organisational effectiveness and human well-being, emphasising the role of work in fostering inclusive, prosperous, and fair societies.
7	<u>DiSK</u>	DiSK is the Turkish Confederation of Progressive Trade Unions.
8	<u>Remote-First Institute</u>	The Remote-First Institute provides resources and support to organisations transitioning to remote-first work models. By focusing on best practices and strategies, the institute helps businesses enhance productivity and flexibility, shaping the future of remote work globally.
9	<u>HUBS</u>	HUBS connects remote workers and digital nomads with local communities in both rural and urban destinations. It designs immersive workation experiences with flexible stays that combine professional productivity, community networking and cultural exploration.

Up until now, the cooperation activities performed with the above projects include actions such as (i) establishment of a Sister Project Collaboration Framework (action that took place among the sister projects); (ii) sharing of reference materials and methodological approaches developed within R-Map's work (action that took place among the sister projects); (iii) participation of external experts in the R-Map Model Validation Workshop, with constructive feedback provided on project outputs; (iv) dissemination of synergies through dedicated posts on the project's social media channels; (v) engagement of external experts in the R-Map's interviews to exchange insights and promote cross-project learning; (vi) online presentations of project activities and/or insights during another project's thematic webinar and in sister projects' Project Meetings; (vii) presentation of synergetic initiative's activities during R-Map's 3rd Project Meetings; (viii) inclusion of

cooperation highlights in project newsletters; (ix) reference of projects in the [dedicated synergies section in the R-Map's website](#); (x) etc.

The synergies leader, with the support of all partners, will continue the efforts to identify new potential collaborations and collaborative actions throughout the project. Future cooperation activities may take various forms. Indicatively:

- Mutual dissemination of events in our SMAs and the website
- Mutual reference of projects on respective websites
- Organisation of joint activities (e.g., workshops, dissemination events, etc.)
- Participation in the project's events
- Exchange of news, experiences
- Co-participating in conferences

Finally, under Task 5.3, a half-a-day (virtual) cluster meeting with the sister projects will take place, as described in DoA, by M26 (March 2026).

Information about the Cluster meeting with sister projects will be included in the updated versions of "D5.1- Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results". More specifically, a short report (2-3 pages) on the outcomes of the cluster meeting, detailing synergistic actions achieved, collaboration needs, and future joint actions will be prepared by M26 and shared with the WP leader to be incorporated in the final version of D5.1 by M36.

8. Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting Framework

8.1 Monitoring and evaluation

In the context of the R-Map project, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms have been fundamental for ensuring the successful execution of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy, which is essential for achieving the project's objectives as outlined in the DCP. To this end, a comprehensive monitoring process was established from the early stages of the project, aimed at identifying any potential gaps, addressing emerging issues and adapting to the evolving needs of stakeholders. This ongoing monitoring has enabled the project team to incorporate best practices, adjust strategies as needed and ensure the effective dissemination of project outcomes to targeted stakeholders and the broader audience.

To measure the impact of DCP activities, KPIs were carefully selected. These have been tailored to project results and integrated into updated deliverables, allowing for the systematic tracking of quantitative metrics throughout reporting periods. Additionally, qualitative feedback has been regularly sought from all consortium partners following events, providing valuable insights for a comprehensive evaluation of the strategy's effectiveness and supporting necessary adjustments. Below is a list of KPIs identified for monitoring the dissemination and communication activities of R-Map.

Table 14. R-Map Key performance indicators.

KPI	M15	M36 Target
Project workshops and events / participants	6/49	12 / ≥ 100
Scientific publications	2 (under review for publishing)	5
External events/conferences attended	10	≥ 15
Synergies with initiatives & networks	≥ 9	≥ 10
Unique visits to project website	878	$\geq 10,000$
Followers in social media	716	$\geq 1,000$
Views of promotional video	2123	≥ 500
Number of newsletters released	2	6
Participants to final dissemination event	N/A	≥ 100
Total number of stakeholders engaged	34,898	50,000

8.2 Reporting

Continuous reporting has been essential to ensuring the successful implementation of R-Map's Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy. Regular documentation of all dissemination and engagement activities contributes to evaluating their effectiveness and, where needed, adjusting efforts to enhance the project's visibility and outreach.

White Research (WR), as the Dissemination and Communication Manager, is responsible for the overall coordination and consolidation of reporting across the consortium. However, all partners are expected to contribute actively by documenting their activities and monitoring the performance of their own communication efforts.

To support this process, three dedicated templates have been developed and shared with the consortium (see Annexes). All partners are expected to fill in the Dissemination Reporting template monthly, logging their actions in the shared project repository. These reports form the basis for the semestrial WP5 contribution to the project's technical reports (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36).

This system enables WR to track both the quantity and quality of activities across partners and ensure the consistency of messaging and branding. In addition to quantitative tracking, qualitative feedback is regularly gathered after key events and dissemination milestones, allowing for timely adjustments to the overall strategy and ensuring alignment with the evolving needs of the project.

To ensure systematic documentation and tracking of dissemination activities, three specific templates have been developed and made available to all partners. These tools support both individual and collective reporting efforts and enable effective monitoring across the project lifecycle. A summary of the templates is provided below:

Table 15. List with Annexes for Dissemination

Dissemination Tool	Annex	Coverage	When
Event’s reporting template	Annex II	Each single event organised by the partners or where the partners participated.	Within 30 days after the implementation of the event
External conferences and Events identification template	Annex III	Any external event/conference that it is relevant to our project and with potential benefit to attend.	Throughout the project (ad- hoc basis)
Dissemination reporting template	Annex IV	All the dissemination activities carried out by the partners every month.	Every month

Event reporting template: This template should be filled by all partners whenever they organise or participate in an event (e.g., workshop, conference, meeting etc.). The template should be sent to WR no later than 30 days after the implementation of the event. Moreover, the events should be always communicated to WR in advance for promotional purposes.

The external conferences and Events template: This is a template that facilitates the identification of events (workshops, conferences, webinars) with topics relevant to the R-Map vision. Each partner should fill in this template and send the information to WR when identifying any event or conference that could be useful for the consortium (e.g., attend, present etc.).

Dissemination reporting template: This template will record all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The online template (online in the project’s repository) will be updated by all partners on a monthly basis (if needed). Keeping track of the activities will ensure that any problems or gaps will be observed early, and mitigation measures will be put in place to be solved.

Each project partner should immediately contact WR, should any risks be identified concerning communication and dissemination activities, or in case problems arise during the implementation of publicity actions.

Furthermore, a dedicated Clustering reporting excel file (see Annex V) has been created by Q-PLAN within the first semester of the project, requesting partners to report their synergies with relevant initiatives, projects and networks. The file is held online in the project’s repository and will be updated by all partners on a monthly basis (if needed). The information collected there has been aggregated by the synergies leader at the end of each semester into a short report describing the activities performed and is incorporated in the semester progress reports.

9. Timeline and implementation plan

Early in the project (M1-M6): In the initial phase of R-Map, our focus was on developing a comprehensive Dissemination & Communication (D&C) strategy tailored to our unique objectives and target audience. During this period, we meticulously identified key stakeholder groups and defined essential project messages to guide our outreach efforts. Metrics for monitoring D&C success were carefully selected and consortium partners were briefed on their roles and contributions to dissemination efforts.

Figure 53. Summary of R-Map's dissemination and communication timeline

Our foremost objective in the early months was to raise awareness about the project's mission and objectives. Within the first months, we established the project's visual identity, including the design of our logo and the accompanying colour palette. Additionally, the SMAs were launched in M2, and the project website was launched in M3. Collaborating with professional graphic designers, we produced vital dissemination materials, such as a leaflet, poster, and templates. While our initial focus remained on broad promotion, we have since started enriching our promotional materials with evidence and success stories, effectively showcasing the project's tangible benefits.

By the end of the sixth month, all project tools and communication channels were fully operational. Additionally, we initiated synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives to amplify our impact. It is noteworthy that by Month 6, we had already released the first of our two project videos, which introduced the aims of the project and drew attention to its significance. This video content continues to support our promotional efforts and contribute to the broader dissemination of R-Map's objectives and activities. This strategic approach has ensured that R-Map gained widespread visibility and laid the foundation for meaningful collaborations in the project's early stages.

During the project (M7-M25): Throughout this phase, R-Map has prioritised establishing continuous and meaningful interaction channels among project partners and relevant stakeholders. A vibrant and engaged community centred around the project's objectives has been cultivated and is being sustained through Social Media Activities, ensuring ongoing engagement and dissemination of project activities.

Our focus during this period has included fostering synergies with other projects and initiatives aligned with the realms of regional development, remote working, and sustainable urban and rural development. Key activities carried out in this phase have encompassed technical and model validation workshops. Also, preparatory actions for the virtual cluster meeting with the sister projects (by M26) will take place.

To ensure wide-reaching impact, we have been regularly publishing and promoting the project's results through the official website and bi-annual newsletters, keeping our stakeholders informed about the progress and achievements of R-Map. Moreover, consortium partners have actively participated in external events and conferences related to regional development, remote working, and sustainability, leveraging their connections to key networks within these sectors. By doing so, we continue to amplify the visibility of the project and its outcomes to a broader audience, contributing to the wider discourse on regional transformations and remote working impacts.

At the end of the project (M26-M36): In the final phase of R-Map, our focus will be on **disseminating the tangible results and impactful outcomes** achieved throughout the project. As we near the conclusion, the wealth of data and insights gathered will empower consortium partners to formulate key recommendations that can pave the way for addressing regional transformation challenges and remote working impacts effectively.

The key activities of this phase include **policy workshops, cross-regional dialogues and policy roundtables** organized within the ongoing dissemination and communication efforts (M25-M36). These events will primarily disseminate the insights and findings from the completed pilot experiments, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration among stakeholders. Additionally, policy recommendations will be developed based on these insights to guide future actions and policies in the realm of regional development and remote working adaptation.

Moreover, an event will be organized to showcase the comprehensive results of R-Map. This event will serve as a platform to engage relevant stakeholders and spark discussions on the post-project utilization of our findings, aiming for sustained impact in the realm of regional development and remote working adaptation.

Finally, **our second promo video** will be launched in M36 communicating and disseminating key research results and key policy recommendations.

Beyond the project (post-M36): Following the conclusion of R-Map, efforts will continue to ensure the sustained impact and utilization of project outcomes. The project's legacy will be preserved through the dissemination of practical guidelines and recommendations derived from the project's findings. These resources will empower stakeholders to implement innovative approaches addressing regional transformation challenges and remote working impacts effectively. Furthermore, **ongoing engagement with stakeholders** will be maintained through various communication channels, including social media platforms and publication of relevant materials. Partnerships forged during the project will be nurtured, fostering continued collaboration and knowledge exchange in the realms of regional development and remote working adaptation.

In addition, the visualization platform developed during the project will remain accessible, providing decision-makers with interactive tools to monitor and assess the effects of RWAs on various aspects of urban and rural regions. Continued utilization of this platform will enable informed decision-making and contribute to the long-term sustainability of regional development efforts. Overall, the legacy of R-Map will endure through ongoing dissemination, collaboration and utilization of project outcomes to drive positive change in regional development and remote working practices. R-Map’s implementation plan is presented in the following table:

Table 16. R-Map's dissemination and communication timeline and objectives

Phase	Objectives	Dissemination tools to be used
1st Phase (M1-M6)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Design the D&C strategy 2. Identify target stakeholder groups and key messages. 3. Prepare the promotional package (leaflet, poster, templates). 4. Brief consortium partners on roles in dissemination efforts. 5. Launch project's website, SMAs and the first promo video. 6. Prepare for technical workshops. 7. Promote widespread awareness of the project. 8. Establish initial synergies with relevant projects, initiatives and networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project’s DCP - Project’s visual identity - Project’s logo and colour palette. - Project’s website - Project’s SMAs - Project’s poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates. - Project’s promo video. - Project’s newsletter - Contact other projects, initiatives and networks - Participation in external events
2nd Phase (M7-M25)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Widely disseminate and communicate the project’s concept and progress. 2. Establish continuous interaction channels with partners and stakeholders. 3. Forge synergies with projects, initiatives and networks aligned with regional development, remote working and sustainability. 4. Build an active community to exchange knowledge and updates on the project and the sector. 5. Cultivate and sustain a vibrant community through SMAs. 6. Promote the adoption of effective strategies and practices to address regional transformation challenges and optimize RWAs, fostering sustainability and resilience across urban and rural areas. 7. Prepare and execute technical workshops, policy roundtables and co-creation workshops. 8. Development of R-Map visualization platform. 9. Prepare the virtual cluster meeting with the sister projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project’s logo - Project’s website - Project’s SMAs - Project’s poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates, Letterheads - Project press release and publications - Project’s Newsletter - Project’s internal events and workshops - Project’s synergies with other relevant projects, initiatives and networks - Participation in external events and conferences
3rd Phase (M26-M36)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Disseminate tangible results and impactful outcomes. 2. Formulate key recommendations for potential outcomes of R-Map. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project’s logo - Project’s website - Project’s SMAs

Phase	Objectives	Dissemination tools to be used
	3. Plan and execute cross-regional dialogues, policy workshops and roundtables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project’s poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates, Letterheads - Project press release and publications - Project’s Newsletter - CoP - Project’s video - Project’s final dissemination event - Project’s synergies with other relevant projects, initiatives and networks including the virtual cluster meeting with the sister projects. - Participation in external events and conferences
4th Phase (Beyond the project)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Continue promoting the project's vision and results. 2. Ensure project's outcomes reach relevant stakeholders. 3. Disseminate project's legacy through relevant publications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium partners' networks and means of communications - Engaged stakeholders

10. Conclusions

The D&C strategy will serve as a guide and will assist the project partners to the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the R-Map project.

Over the first 15 months of implementation, R-Map's dissemination and communication efforts have been dynamic, targeted, and impactful. The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) has served as a strategic and operational guide, ensuring the project's visibility across multiple stakeholder groups and channels while evolving based on practical experience and feedback.

The consortium successfully established a strong project identity, including a coherent visual and communication style supported by promotional materials such as the project logo, leaflet, poster, publication templates, and a promotional video. The R-Map website was launched early and has served as the central hub for project updates, publications, and stakeholder engagement, complemented by a bi-annual newsletter and regular content updates.

Our social media strategy has proven highly effective, with LinkedIn emerging as the cornerstone of our digital outreach. By April 8th, 2025, we had achieved 42,540 impressions and 5,429 interactions on LinkedIn, successfully building a professional community of 561 followers. Complementary activity across Facebook, YouTube, and the emerging Bluesky platform further extended our reach. Regular monitoring via Metricool and Google Analytics enabled ongoing evaluation and adaptation of our digital presence.

We engaged actively through both internal and external events. Several technical workshops, a full-day model validation workshop, and advisory board consultations strengthened internal collaboration and project development. Meanwhile, participation in major external conferences and forums helped to position R-Map within relevant scientific and policy communities, establishing valuable networks and synergies.

Throughout this period, the active participation of all consortium partners has been crucial to our success. By coordinating efforts and continuously refining our strategy, we ensured that R-Map's key messages reached policymakers, public sector officials, civil servants, academics, researchers, policy advisors, consultants working on policy development, urban planning & remote work strategies as well as business leaders and remote workers across Europe.

Our enhanced communication strategy, featuring a news-driven, audience-focused approach, valuable website enhancements, and a robust rapid-response workflow, ensures strategic outreach, transparency, and continual refinement. The report outlines the consortium's coordinated efforts to date, with performance metrics highlighting strong results. By targeting diverse audiences, from policymakers and industry to students and remote workers, we've successfully made R-Map's insights and achievements more visible, relevant, and impactful.

Moving forward, the DCP will continue to be a living document, guiding ongoing dissemination activities while building on the momentum created so far. We remain committed to increasing visibility, fostering stakeholder engagement, and ensuring the wide and lasting impact of R-Map's findings, tools, and policy recommendations.

This updated version has been produced by M15, while the final revised version will be prepared by M36, reinforcing the project's vision and extending its impact across the wider European community.

11. Annexes

Annex I – Dissemination and communication guidelines.

Overview

→ Actively contribute to the dissemination of project results and key messages.

→ Please use the wording “R-Map” to refer to the project.

→ Please don't forget to **always include the EU logo** and the disclaimer.

In practice, it should look like this:

When displayed with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. The EU emblem, and the funding statement, must be featured on all communication material such as printed, digital products, websites and their mobile version, for the public or the partners.

- More information on how to display the EU logo in publications and products can be found [here](#)
- You can download the EU emblem in the desired resolution following this link: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en.

- ✓ Partners are requested to carefully follow the above instructions, as they are a contractual obligation, (Article 17 of the GA).
- ✓ In compliance with the GA (Article 17), any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view, and that the EC Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.
- ✓ If possible, follow the style guide concerning writing style, formatting options, numbers and currency, abbreviations and acronyms, captions, electronic cross-references, naming conventions, citation style.

In general:

- ❖ Make sure to use the logo colour scheme for documents in order to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project.
- ❖ Always use the same style for references, both for in-text citations and in the bibliography/footnotes.
- ❖ Be consistent in using currency references (for example, use EUR instead of € throughout).
- ❖ Be consistent in the numbering format; comply with the British usage (e.g., 75,000,239.23), unless differently indicated.
- ❖ If you abbreviate a word, use the correct abbreviation (for instance, 'm' for million, not 'mn').

- ❖ Make sure to introduce each abbreviation and acronym the first time you use it and create an abbreviation/acronym list at the beginning of the document.
- ❖ Review the language and the coherence of the structure of the text you drafted.
- ✓ Whenever possible, use the templates that will be provided to you, e.g., letterhead, presentation, publication. A leaflet and a poster will be prepared for you to use throughout the project. Other communication materials (e.g., infographics) will be prepared ad-hoc if needed.
- ✓ **Always** inform WR regarding every dissemination and communication activity that you plan to carry out (e.g., organisation of an event, articles on websites or magazines, participation in an external event, etc.). This will enable us to publicise it through the project's communication channels in a timely manner.
- ✓ You will have to report in detail all the dissemination actions you undertook (please see **R-Map Dissemination Reporting Template** for instructions).
- ✓ Always report about meetings and events you organised and/or participated in (please see **R-Map Event Reporting Template** for an explanation on how to report about events).
- ✓ Inform WR about relevant events (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) in which R-MAP partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. An Excel (.xls) file named "**R-Map External Conferences and Events**" has been uploaded in the project repository. All partners are kindly requested to fill in this specific Excel file, each time they identify an event relevant to project and share it with WR.
- ✓ In compliance with GDPR requirements, always gather stakeholders' consent, when collecting, using and storing personal data during events/conferences. Please consider that pictures which make individuals identifiable are also considered personal data. Partners are responsible to gather participants' consent for the activities they undertake.

The above-mentioned points will be updated, when necessary, in order to be in line with the project's requirements and progress. The R-Map report "Dissemination and Communication Plan" (First version due in M3) includes these guidelines and will also outline the overall project's dissemination strategy and plan.

Dissemination Monitoring Tools

1. R-Map Dissemination reporting template

The Dissemination reporting template is an Excel file (online in the project's repository) that has to be updated in a monthly basis by all consortium partners. All the information required must be provided; the European Commission collects all these data from the Dissemination Manager. Therefore, for each activity please indicate:

- Date
- Place
- Short description
- Type of activity
- Online/physical
- Title

- If the activity is part of the project
- Role and description of the organisation's involvement
- Other project partners involved
- Type of audience
- Size of audience per type of stakeholder group
- Countries addressed
- Gender of audience
- Type of material used and quantity (e.g. number of flyers distributed)
- Other partners or external organisation involved
- Short description of action and dissemination activities
- Other comments
- Relevant contacts made (if consent was given)

2. R-Map internal events and Reporting Template

The event report (online in the project's repository) has to be sent after every event within 30 days to WR. It is a structured file that includes:

- Event data (title, date, venue, organisers, type and number of attendants, duration).
- Goals and relevance within the project.
- Organisation.
- Dissemination activities.
- Short minutes of the events (structure).
- Outcomes of the event.
- Evaluation.
- Appendixes (list of participants and scanned copy of the list signed by all participants– if possible, in compliance with the GDPR, agenda, photos, presentations).

3. External Conferences and Events

This is an Excel file (online in the project's repository), that you can fill in each time you identify an event (e.g. conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) relevant to R-Map and in which R-Map partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. Please share it with White Research.

4. Clustering reporting excel file

This is an Excel file (available online in the project's repository), that all partners can fill at the end of each month (if needed) or each time they deploy a collaborative action with a relevant project, initiative or network. It consists of the sheets: (i) Relevant Initiatives; (ii) Clustering; (iii) X Initiative's Info, Y Initiative's Info, Z Initiative's Info etc.; (iv) KPI.

Sheet "Relevant Initiatives": This is a sheet that you need to fill in each time you identify new relevant projects, networks, initiatives or research efforts of mutual interest during the implementation of the project.

Sheet "Clustering": This is a sheet that you need to fill in each time after you deploy a collaborative action with a relevant project, network, initiative or research effort.

Sheet "X Initiative's Info": This is a sheet that you need to fill in with the information of the project you collaborated with, the possible activities of collaboration and the current status of your progress (after renaming the sheet's title using the name of the project you collaborated with).

Sheet "KPI": This is a sheet that the synergies leader will update in order to count the synergies R-Map has established with initiatives & networks.

Guidelines for enhancing online presence of R-Map

This section provides you with some key initial guidelines regarding your expected contribution and use of the R-Map website and SMAs.

Website

1. Collect photos and videos for all R-Map activities and share them with White Research, so as to make them usable on the website and on the R-Map SMAs.
2. Actively contribute (if possible, with 1 news item per month per partner) to the news section of the website. Please send each news item to White Research.
3. A news item can be anything, like a link to other similar projects/activities, an article about a new regulation, a notice regarding a new policy or initiative, an article about an event etc.
4. Inform White Research regarding every event you organise or take part to for the purposes of the project (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) and provide White Research with a link to the event, so that it can be posted online in the dedicated section of the website.
5. Inform White Research about news articles (e.g., newspaper article, blogpost, TV interview etc.) mentioning the R-MAP project and provide White Research with a link/scan for giving it more visibility online.

Social Media Accounts

1. Register for all R-MAP SMAs (e.g., Facebook, X, LinkedIn and YouTube) and use them: monitor announcements and posts, comment, like and retweet.
2. Do make your own posts to foster discussion and keep the page alive.
3. Promote the R-MAP SMAs within your network of contacts.
4. Signal to White Research relevant profiles that we could follow (on Facebook, X, LinkedIn).

5. If you make a short video edit it so as to enhance the project identity (add the name of the project, the logo, the EU emblem and the disclaimer “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101136427”). White Research will upload it on YouTube.

The above-mentioned points will be updated, when necessary, in order to be in line with the project’s requirements and progress.

R-Map social media accounts	
Facebook	R-Map Project EU
LinkedIn	R-Map Project EU
YouTube	R-Map Project EU
Bluesky	R-Map Project EU
X	R-Map Project EU

Annex II - Event's reporting template

Event's Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Organisers	
Audience (number and type)	
Duration	

Stakeholders reached

What type of stakeholders were engaged?

- Define the type(s) of stakeholders reached (policy, SMEs, general public etc.)
- How many people attended?

Event's goals, objectives and relevance with R-Map

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g. to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc.). Was the event relevant to R-Map?

Organization of the event

In case of organizing a project's event. For participation in external events do not complete this section.

How was the event/activity organized?

- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

Dissemination activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? Was the R-Map project promoted during the event?

Structure of the event (short minutes)

Description of the event's sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

What ideas were generated? (brief explanations are sufficient)

Evaluation of the event

What are the main impressions and observations that you made?

- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

ANNEX: Attachments

- The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if possible)
- The agenda of the event
- Photos (please make sure to have the consent of participants to use them)
- Presentations (if applicable)
- Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g., links to press releases, videos, posts, leaflets etc.)

Annex III- External conferences and events identification template

NO	Event's name	Date	Location (City/Country)	Registration fees (if applicable)	Registration Deadline	Organiser(s)	Link	Partner participating	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission,...)
1	International Conference on "Changing Cities" Conference on Urban, Regional Planning and	24-28/06/24	Rhodos Island, Greece				https://changingcities.prd.uth.gr/cc/	TBD	

Figure 54. External conferences and events identification template

Annex IV- Dissemination Reporting Template

		Basic Info			Activity details				
No. of Action	Partner	Date of activity	Place of activity	Short description of the action	Type of activity <i>(Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)</i>	Was the activity online?	Title of conference, workshop, publication, website article, etc.	Is the activity part of the R-MAP project?	Role and description of your organisation's involvement <i>(e.g. organiser, facilitator, interviewer, speaker, discussant, author, participant, etc.)</i>
Audience of the event /activity									
Other R-MAP partners involved (use N/A if not applicable)	Government and Policy Institutions	Business Associations and Decision Makers	Workers	Researchers & Academia	Urban Design and Development Experts	Civil Society	Media	Investors	Customers
					Material used		Other		
Customers	Other	Overall No of participants	Gender of Audience <i>(no of women)</i>	Countries addressed	Type of R-MAP material used	Quantity of project material used <i>(no. of copies distributed per type of project material)</i>	Other comments <i>(IF RELEVANT)</i>	Significant contacts made <i>IF RELEVANT (name, position, organisation; add also address, tel, e-mail)</i>	

Figure 55. Dissemination Reporting Template

Annex V - Clustering Reporting Excel File

No	Name of Initiative, project, network	Suggested by	Type of initiative, project, network (Horizon Europe)	Short description	Website	Country	Geographic scope (Regional, National, European, International)	Type of stakeholders / target group (e.g. remote workers, advisors, academia, public)	Contact details: Name	Contact details: Role	Contact details: E-mail	Any previous contact? (Yes/No)	Potential joint activities	Comments
1	REMAKING	Q-PLAN	Sister project - Horizon Europe project	REMAKING aims at delivering a policy-oriented framework reflecting the new and multi-faceted realities of RW, facilitating policymakers to adopt place-based policies balancing the opportunities and risks of RW and sharing practices to foster mutual learning on RW in the novel scenario of WinWin4Worklife envisions to enable healthy, inclusive and sustainable remote working arrangements (RWA) in Europe by combining employer and employee perspectives into a single framework. To do so, WinWin4WorkLife will collect novel and comprehensive data in 5 European	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-opportunities/portals	-	European	remote workers, advisors, academia, public	tba	tba	tba	No	1. Clustering event with sister projects 2. participation in workshops? 3. present themselves in	PC (AUTH) suggested during KoM that they communicate with the PO first and ask him to initiate the first
2	WinWin4WorkLife	Q-PLAN	Sister project - Horizon Europe project	WinWin4Worklife envisions to enable healthy, inclusive and sustainable remote working arrangements (RWA) in Europe by combining employer and employee perspectives into a single framework. To do so, WinWin4WorkLife will collect novel and comprehensive data in 5 European	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-opportunities/portals	-	European	advisors, academia, public authorities	tba	tba	tba	No	1. Clustering event with sister projects 2. participation in workshops? 3. present themselves in	PC (AUTH) suggested during KoM that they communicate with the PO first and ask him to initiate the first

Relevant Initiatives Clustering X Initiative's Info Z Initiative's Info REMAKING WW4WL REMOTE-IT MOBI-TWIN Future of Work Remc

Figure 56. Relevant Initiatives sheet

N°	Period	Date	Cooperation with project	Action/Activity Type	Partner involved	Clustering Action/Activity title	Location	Objectives / Info of action or activity	Comments
1	01/02/2024 - 31/07/2024	31 May 2024	MOBI-TWIN	Post	WR	Posts on R-Map's social media announcing synergy	Linkedin, Fb, X	Announcement of the collaboration and presentation of MOBI-TWIN project. Following one of MOBI-TWIN from the previous day	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/r-map-project-eu_home-r-map-activity-7202217783516884992-pchv?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
2	01/02/2024 - 31/07/2024	13 June 2024	REMAKING	Input	AUTH	T1.2 Interview with experts	virtual meeting	Vasilis Avdikos, expert working on REMAKING, participated in an interview regarding the spatial impacts of remote work	
3	01/02/2024 - 31/07/2024	20 June 2024	REMAKING	Input	AUTH	T1.2 Interview with experts	virtual meeting	Ilaria Mariotti, expert working on REMAKING, participated in an interview regarding the spatial impacts of remote work.	The participant is also partner in project MOBI-TWIN
4	01/02/2024 - 31/07/2024	21 June 2024	REMAKING	Input	SURREY	T1.4 Interview with 2 experts	virtual meeting	Ilaria Mariotti and Federica Maria Rossi, experts working on REMAKING, participated in an interview regarding the socio-economic impacts of remote work.	SURREY and Q-PLAN participated The participants are also partners in project MOBI-TWIN
5	01/02/2024 - 31/07/2024	5 July 2024	REMOTE-IT network	Webinar	AUTH	Online presentation in "Remote Work and Green Transition" webinar	virtual meeting	AUTH presented the R-map project, its objectives and expected results, focusing on the sustainability dimension - webinar "Remote Work and Green Transition"	AUTH and SEERC participated
6	01/02/2024 - 31/07/2024	10 July 2024	WinWin4WorkLife	Input	SURREY	T1.4 interview	virtual meeting	The Project Co-ordinator participated in a T1.4 case study interview	
7	01/02/2024 - 31/07/2024	10 July 2024	WinWin4WorkLife	Input	AUTH	Input for the website of WinWin4WorkLife	email	AUTH sent to WinWin4WorkLife the logo of R-Map, a short description of the project and the URL of the website to be used	

Figure 57. Clustering Activities sheet

Project		Full project name	
Website		Scope	
Contact person		Organisation	
E-mail			
Connections of R-Map with <Insert Project's Title>			
List of potential future joint actions between R-Map and <Insert Project's Title> (as discussed in bilateral meetings, emails)		When	
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			
Current status			
What has been done (coordination activities, such as meetings, etc.)		Who	When

< > ...
Relevant Initiatives
Clustering
X Initiative's Info
Z Initiative's Info
REMAKING
WW4WL
RE

Figure 58. Initiative's Info sheet

GA 101132497

Partners

Partners

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